

	<u>Word Initial, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Final</u>	<u>Word Final, Syl Final</u>
/Vb/ Morphemic	/gɪ+ba:r+id+e/	/bueɣ+žɪab+ɪ/	/gɪ+trúeb+t+iw/	/diwʊn+ižɪ-wi:b/
Assign stress	[gɪ+bá:r+id+e]	[búeɣ+žɪàb+ɪ]	[gɪ+trúeb+t+iw]	[díwʊn+ižɪ-wi:b]
Syllabification	[gɪ.bá:.rɪ.de]	[búeɣ.žɪà.bɪ]	[gɪ.trúeb.tiw]	[dí.wʊ.ni.žɪwɪ:b]
Raising				
Rounding			[gɪ.trúeb.tü:]	
Words assembled				
Fronting	[gɪ.bǣ:.rɪ.de]			
V-Reduction	[gɪ.bǣ:.rɪ̃.de]			[dí.wʊ.nɪ̃.žɪwɪ:b]
Fortition	[kɪ.bǣ:.rɪ̃.de]	[púeɣ.štà.bɪ]		[dí.wʊ.nɪ̃.štɪwɪ:b]
Assimilation				
Epenthesis				
Lenition				
C-Reduction				
Elision	[kɪ.bǣ:r.de]			
Lowering				
Speech->Writing	<ke bārda>	<pūoh stábe>	<ge trûobtíu>	<díonest uuíb>
Variation		<pūoh stabe>	<ge trûoptíu>	
Miniscule	Tisêr decoratus uuás fautor gothorum . pe\diu uuás er méldâre dero ciuium . Uuánda er óuh tār mi\te spílománnes kebārda hábeta .	Áfter díen man stígen máhti . fólne demo níderen pūohstabe zu demo óberen . Uuánda sancti únde \ sapientes .	Sélbíu diu lúft uuíder \ dia érda getrûoptíu . fône dero óberún uuármi . únde fône de\ro níderun názi .	Vnz sí dáz ál uuórh̄ta . sô gesáh íro díonest-uuíb periergia . dáz-tir \ ch̄it studiosa operatrix . fúre sía sórgendíu .
Etymology	Gmc */gabarja-/	Gmc */bōka-/, */staba-/	Gmc */drōbja-/	Gmc */pewanōsta-/, */weiba-/
OHG lexeme	gibārīda, 27	buohstab, 44	truoben, 40	dionōstwīb, 2
MHG lexeme	gebārde	buochstap	trüeben	dienestwīp
Latin gloss	'gestus'	'littera'	'turbare'	'fabula'
German gloss	'Gebärde'	'Buchstabe'	'trüben'	'Dienstfrau'
English gloss	'gesture'	'letter'	'make anxious'	'maid'
Class	Noun str (ō)	Noun str (a)	Verb wk (ja), past part	Noun str, (a)
Inflection	fem acc sg	masc dat sg	fem nom sg	fem nom sg
Citattation	Nb12414 : I, 146, 13	Nb00906 : I, 10, 31	Nc14305 : I, 823 , 30	Nc10103 : I, 783, 28
Notes	Think of <béren> in Notker, and the English verb <i>bear</i> . Note that the Germanic reconstruction shows a short /a/, which must lengthen. <kebārda> has elision, but Notker also writes <ida> in <beskérīda, gírīda, stórīda>. What might be the difference?	See that word boundary for spelling rules applies between elements of a compound, and even after prefixes. So [x] is written <h> in <pūoh> here, and not the word internal spelling <ch> in <būoche>. Why?	Continuing with <būoh>, see <būohlísto> from Boethius with <būochscríft> from the Psalms. One manuscript enforces the spelling rules less consistently. Why might that be?	The <íō> is easier if disyllabic, but <est/ōst> is hard. Comparatives and superlatives (English <i>-er</i> and <i>-est</i>) could either have an /i/ or /o:/ vowel. Or are variants with <ōst> from maybe the stem vowel /o:/ in <díenōn> 'serve'?

	<u>Word Initial, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Final</u>	<u>Word Final, Syl Final</u>
/Vp/ Morphemic	/gɪ/+/purpʊr/+/o:t+ʊ/	Not Found	/na:h/+/ʒɪpp+e/	Not Found
Assign stress	[gɪ]+[pʊrpʊr]+[o:t+ʊ]		[ná:h]+[ʒɪpp+e]	
Syllabification	[gɪ]+[pʊr.pʊr]+[o:.tʊ]		[ná:h].[ʒɪp.pe]	
Raising				
Rounding				
Words assembled	[gɪ.pʊr.pʊ.ro:.tʊ]		[ná:h.ʒɪp.pe]	
Fronting				
V-Reduction	[gɪ.pʊr.pʊ.rʊ.tʊ]			
Fortition			[ná:h.ʃɪp.pe]	
Assimilation				
Epenthesis				
Lenition				
C-Reduction				
Elision				
Lowering				
Speech->Writing	<ge_purpuroto>		<nâh síppa>	
Variation	<ge-purperoto>			
Miniscule	er lêret sie iz pedénchen . \ der ge- purperoto richo pegrábin in bello \ Er ságet ín uuiêo díues purpuratus uuard sepultus in inferno .		dóh sie reprobi sin . Fone dién ánderes-uuâr also der lílio ist undir dórnin also ist mîn nâh\síppa gescriben ist	
Etymology	ELat <purpura>		Gmc */nēhwa-/, */sebjō-/	
OHG lexeme	purpurōn, 1		nāhsippa, 1	
MHG lexeme	Not found		nachsippe	
Latin gloss	'purpurare'		'proxima'	
German gloss	'in Purpur kleiden'		'Vertraute'	
English gloss	'dress in purple'		'confidante'	
Class	Verb wk (ō), past part		Noun wk (n)	
Inflection	masc nom sg wk		fem nom sg	
Citattation	Np25619 : II, 289, 6		Np16601 : II, 183, 3	
Notes	Here is our first borrowing from Ecclesiastical Latin (ELat). Your writer sees these words pronounced with Old Alemannic sound rules. Others disagree. What could be arguments in either direction?	See entries here under Words assembled, which marks the moment that Notker spoke the phrase. This convention allows us to show sound changes before Notker, like raising and rounding.	Both roots of <nâh síppa> are Germanic, but the word only occurs once in OHG (hence <i>nāhsippa, 1</i>). So maybe it was not a native compound, but one assembled by Notker.	Here is the great question with Words assembled. Should other lines appear above it, especially Fronting and V-Reduction? Would that make umlauted vowels phonemic in Notker? If not, what two umlauted vowels are phonemic in Notker, one short and one long?

	<u>Word Initial, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Final</u>	<u>Word Final, Syl Final</u>
/Vv/ Morphemic	/gɪ+var+t+j+ɪn/	/lug+j+/brɪev+ɪn/	/gɪ+brɪev+t+ɪ/	/brɪev+/buɛx+ɪ/
Assign stress	/gɪ+vár+t+j+ɪn/	[lúg+j]+[brɪev+ɪn]	[gɪ+brɪev+t+ɪ]	[brɪev]+[búɛx+ɪ]
Syllabification	[gɪ.vár.tjɪn]	[lú.gjɪ]+[brɪe.vɪn]	[gɪ.brɪev.tɪ]	[brɪev]+[búɛ.xɪ]
Raising	[gɪ.vär.tjɪn]			
Rounding				
Words assembled		[lú.gjɪ.brɪe.vɪn]		[brɪev.búɛ.xɪ]
Fronting		[lú.gjɪ.brɪe.vɪn]		
V-Reduction	[gɪ.vär.tən]	[lú.gɪ.brɪe.vən]		
Fortition			[kɪ.brɪev.tɪ]	[brɪev.púɛ.xɪ]
Assimilation				
Epenthesis				
Lenition				
C-Reduction				
Elision				
Lowering				
Speech->Writing	<ge <u>u</u> érten>	<lúge br <u>ɪ</u> eu <u>e</u> n>	<ke br <u>ɪ</u> eu <u>f</u> te>	<br <u>ɪ</u> eu <u>f</u> pu <u>o</u> che>
Variation	<ge <u>f</u> érten>			<br <u>ɪ</u> eu <u>f</u> pu <u>o</u> che>
Miniscule	Uli\xes chlāgeta sine geferten . die imo in sicilia der rīso poliphemus uuōti\go frāz .	fōne dien \ lúge-brɪeu <u>e</u> n ze_sāgenne . mīt tien sie mih zihent uuellen uuide\re guuūnnen úmbe den chéiser dia rúmiskūn sélb- uuáltigi?	sō cadmus íst filius agenoris . eneas únde romulus . kebr <u>ɪ</u> eu <u>f</u> te góta hiezin . Únde ándere dár- míte .	Deleantur de libro uiuentium . Ábe[r] déro \ lébenton br <u>ɪ</u> eu <u>f</u> pu <u>o</u> che uuérden sie gescaben .
Etymology	Gmc */fardi-/	Gmc */lugi/, VLat <brevis>	VLat <brevis>	VLat <brevis>, Gmc */bōka-/
OHG lexeme	giferto, 14	lugibrief, 1	briefen, 14	briefbuoh, 2
MHG lexeme	geverte	Not found	briefen	briefbuoch
Latin gloss	'comes'	'litterae falsae'	'perscribere'	'liber (documentorum)'
German gloss	'Gefährte'	'lügnerisches Schreiben'	'verzeichnen'	'Urkundenbuch'
English gloss	'companion'	'deceitful letter'	'register'	'book of deeds'
Class	Noun masc wk (n)	Noun masc str (a)	Verb wk (ja), past part	Noun str (a)
Inflection	acc pl	dat pl	masc nom pl	dat sg
Citotation	Nb22809 : I, 298, 18	Nb02511 : I, 31, 4	Nc08407 : I, 767, 24	Np24110 : II, 271, 18
Notes	Did you catch the cheating, where we stick a /j/ in to raise /a/ to [ä]? It gets harder when the raised vowel is word final, as in <uáren, u <u>é</u> rt> German <i>fahren, f<u>á</u>hrt</i> in Notker's <uuíderu <u>é</u> rt> 'return'.	More cheating with another /j/, but you also see how */fardi-/ and */lugi/ ended historically. And we have our first Vulgar Latin borrowing, as it comes in with the vowel <íe>, not <é> in *<br <u>é</u> uen>.	Why should the <f> in <br <u>ɪ</u> eu <u>f</u> te be the regular spelling and not <br <u>ɪ</u> eu <u>t</u> e? What might have been Notker's motivation?	Notker is highly creative, and a delight to read. See how he translates the Book of Life in Revelations, into a one of the few books that his students, many children of villagers, may have been familiar with.

	<u>Word Initial, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Final</u>	<u>Word Final, Syl Final</u>
/Vf/ Morphemic	/gɪ/+/fʊntɛmɪntt/+/o:+t+o:ʒt/	/tɪɛf+ir+ɛ/	/vir+xɛwɪf+t+ɪmʊ/	/xorn/+/xɛwɪf/
Assign stress	[gɪ]+[fʊntɛmɪntt]+[o:+t+o:ʒt]	[tɪɛf+ir+ɛ]	[vir+xɛwɪf+t+ɪmʊ]	[xorn]+[xɛwɪf]
Syllabification	[gɪ]+[fʊn.tɛ.mɪntt]+[o:.to:ʒt]	[tɪɛ.fɪ.re]	[vir.xɛwɪf.tɪ.mʊ]	
Raising				
Rounding			[vir.xɔwɪf.tɪ.mʊ]	[xorn]+[xɔwɪf]
Words assembled	[gɪ.fʊn.tɛ.mɪnt.tɔ:.to:ʒt]			[xorn.xɔwɪf]
Fronting				
V-Reduction	[gɪ.fʊn.tɛ.mɛnt.tʊ.to:ʒt]	[tɪɛ.fɪr.e]	[vɛr.xɔwɪf.tɪ.mʊ]	
Fortition	[kɪ.fʊn.tɛ.mɛnt.tʊ.to:ʒt]		[fɛr.xɔwɪf.tɪ.mʊ]	
Assimilation	[kɪ.fʊn.tɛ.mɛnt.tʊ.to:ʒt]			[xɔrn.xɔwɪf]
Epenthesis				[xɔrnk.xɔwɪf]
Lenition	[kɪ.fʊn.dɛ.mɛnt.tʊ.to:ʒt]			
C-Reduction				[xɔrnk.xɔwɪf]
Elision				
Lowering				
Speech->Writing	<ke fʊndamentotost>	<tɪɛfera>	<fer chɔuftemo>	<chorn chɔuf>
Variation	<ke fundamentotost>	<tiɛfera>	<fer chouftemo>	
Miniscule	Den erdering . unde al daz dâr in\ne ist ! kefundamentotost dû . fone diû uualtest dû iro .	Vnde \ uuaxzer-diêfina uuûrden getruôbet . daz sint hominum consci\entie . Vuaz mag tiêfera sin?	uendito CHRISTO (ferchouftemo) . hiêr ist aber dominus (Got) ad (ze) dexteram (zeseuun) pauperis (des armin) . daz selber dominus (Got)	Tô in_hândegên hûnger-iâren strénge chorn-chɔuf in \ campania . unde úbelêr ze_geuuéren . unde día sêlbûn gebûrda \ er-ârmén súlendêr .
Etymology	ELat <fundamentum>	Gmc */deupa-/	CLat <caupo>	Gmc */kurna-/, CLat <caupo>
OHG lexeme	fundamentôn, 1	tiof, 46	firkoufen, 42	kornkouf, 1
MHG lexeme	fundamënt (noun)	tief	verkoufen	kornkouf
Latin gloss	'fundare'	'profundus'	'venundare'	'coemptio'
German gloss	'mit Fundament versehen '	'tief'	'verkaufen'	'Getreideaufkauf'
English gloss	'set the foundation'	'deep'	'sell'	'grain purchase'
Class	Verb wk (ō).	Adj.	Verb wk (ja), past part.	Noun str (a).
Inflection	2nd sg past	neut nom sg comp wk	masc dat sg	masc nom sg
Citation	Np32515: II, 368, 26	Np27422 : II, 310, 11	Np41524 : II, 475, 5	Nb02205 : I, 27, 1
Notes	This <f> is never written <u> in Notker, even when preceded by a sonorant. Is that because <fʊndamentôn> starts with /f/, or does it start with /v/ and <f> is just written on analogy with Latin?	Here is a first example of the comparative as /ir/. In an upcoming form, <spâtôr> 'later', you will see the variant /o:r/.	<choufen> could start with either /x/ or /kx/, per the principle of Posit as Little as Possible. C-Reduction creates <chouf> with /x/ or /kx/, but <ferchouftemo> only works with /x/. Why is that?	Try pronouncing this [xɔrnk.xɔwɪf], to get a feeling for how Swiss German dialects are so unintelligible to your writer, a native American, who only learned standard German. And also, some words are just fun to say.

	<u>Word Initial, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Final</u>	<u>Word Final, Syl Final</u>
/Vpf/ Morphemic	/publɪtse:/+/pfla:g+i:n/	/untər/+/ʒtʊpf+jɛ+t/	/ʒlɪpf/+/t+o:n/	/ʒtʊpf/
Assign stress	[públɪtse:]+[pflá:g+i:n]	[ún.tər]+[ʒtúpf+jɛ+t]	[ʒlɪpf]+[to:n]	[ʒtúpf]
Syllabification	[pú.blɪ.tse:]+[pflá:.gi:n]	[ún.tər]+[ʒtú.pfjɛt]	[ʒlɪpf]+[to:n]	
Raising				
Rounding				
Words assembled	[pú.blɪ.tse:.pflá:.gi:n]	[ún.tər.ʒtù.pfjɛt]	[ʒlɪpf.to:n]	
Fronting	[pú.blɪ.tse:.pflǣ:.gi:n]	[ún.tər.ʒtù.pfjɛt]		
V-Reduction	[pú.blɪ.tse:.pflǣ:.gi:n]	[ún.tər.ʒtù.pfɛt]		
Fortition		[ún.tər.ʃtù.pfɛt]		[ʃtúpf]
Assimilation		[ún.tər.ʃtù.pfɛt]		
Epenthesis				
Lenition		[ún.dər.ʃtù.pfɛt]		
C-Reduction				
Elision				
Lowering				
Speech->Writing	<publice flâgîn>	<únder stúpfet>	<slíftôn>	<stúpf>
Variation		<úndir stúpfít>		
Miniscule	únde éinzên \ áfter hértō dero rei publice flâgîn . Proconsules uuâren in loco consulum . Pontifices flâgen dero reliḡionis .	uuânda ér mág úndir stúpfít \ uuérdin . únde dér stúpf íst tãnne geméine \ mârcha des zéseuuin téilis .	Vnde so mine fuôzze sih uuégeton . dax \ chit so siê slífton . so chôseton sie fône mir mícheliu .	nôh sâr \ ze_énde dero smálun érdo geréichôntes . díu éin stúpf íst \ uuíder demo hímele .
Etymology	Gmc */plegan/	Gmc */stuppja-/	Gmc */slippja-/	Gmc */stuppa-/
OHG lexeme	pflegan, 19	untarstupfen, 1	slipfen, 14	stupf, 24
MHG lexeme	phlëgen	Not found	slipfen	stupf
Latin gloss	'curare'	'terminum communem sumere'	'labi'	'punctum'
German gloss	'sorgen für'	'unterteilen'	'ausgleiten'	'Punkt'
English gloss	'take care of'	'subdivide'	'slip'	'point'
Class	Verb str (5)	Verb wk (ja), past part	Verb wk (ja)	Noun str (a)
Inflection	3rd pl pres subj	uninflected	3rd pl past	masc nom sg
Citation	Nx12345 : I, 614, 12	Nk04215 : I, 400, 25	Np12906 : II, 139, 19	Nb10209 : I, 118, 11
Notes	Here is a spelling rule where [pf] gets written <f> at the beginning of a word. What would motivate Notker to do that? Also, that <ę> is an e-caudata in ELatin. Any idea on what it was in Classical Latin (CLatin)? In Notker's ELatin, the <c> is [ts] before it.	Frequently, this second column will feature a morpheme affected by a following vowel, often /j/ or /i/. The fourth column will have that morpheme without anything following it.	Your writer sees the dental preterite (-ed in English), as originally a separate word. It is as if people said 'slip did' before 'slipped'.	Continuing with the dental preterite to the left. How does positioning Words assembled after Raising affect a verb with /a/ in the stem, in the past subjunctive, where the /t/ is followed by an /i:/?

	<u>Word Initial, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Final</u>	<u>Word Final, Syl Final</u>
/lb/ Morphemic	/him+il/+/bro:t+ɪ/	/unbɪ+halb+o:/+/t+o:n/	Not Found	/ʒunt+halb/
Assign stress	[hím+ił]+[bró:t+ɪ]	[únbɪ+hàlb+o:]+[t+o:n]		[žúnt+hàlb]
Syllabification	[hí.mīł]+[bró:.tɪ]	[ún.bɪ.hàl.bo:]+[to:n]		[žúnt.hàlb]
Raising				
Rounding				
Words assembled	[hí.mīł.brò:.tɪ]	[ún.bɪ.hàl.bo:.to:n]		
Fronting				
V-Reduction	[hí.mīl.brò:.tɪ]	[ún.bɪ.hàl.bʊ.to:n]		
Fortition				
Assimilation		[úm.bɪ.hàl.bʊ.to:n]		[žúnt.hàlb]
Epenthesis				
Lenition				
C-Reduction				
Elision				
Lowering				
Speech->Writing	<hímil brôte>	<úmbe hálbótôn>		<súnt hálb>
Variation	<himel brôte>	<umbe halboton>		
Miniscule	Et pane celi . i . manna saturavit eos . Vnde mit himel-brôte gesátota er siê . Daz pezêichenda christum fone himele chómenen .	Mih dīnen liūt . chit ecclesia . umbehalboton alle diēte . unde in dīnen \ námen úberuuant ih siê .		sámo-so ába-fersnítenen taurum \ ze dien lánchon . Mít tien béinen tréttot ér cētum . tér ímo súnt\hálb íst .
Etymology	Gmc */hemila-/ */brauda-/	Gmc */umbi/, */halba-/		Gmc */sunpa/, */halba-/
OHG lexeme	himilbrôt, 3	umbihalbōn, 6		sundhalb, 2
MHG lexeme	himelbrôt	umbehalben		Not found
Latin gloss	'panis caeli'	'circumdare'		'meridianus'
German gloss	'Himmelsbrot'	'umgeben'		'südlich von'
English gloss	'manna'	'surround'		'south of'
Class	Noun str (a).	Verb wk (ō).		Adv.
Inflection	neut dat sg	3rd pl past		uninflected
Citation	Np39403 : II, 449, 20	Np43403 : II 494, 18		NC06611 : I, 751, 2
Notes	Here the second part of <hímil> is an affix /him+il/, maybe 'little home'. How would it be spelled if treated as an unstressed, second element of the root, so /hímil/? Which is correct? Entries in Notker's Psalms point one way, other manuscripts the other way.	Should <úmbe> be broken into two morphemes? Maybe think of English words like <i>ambidextrous</i> or <i>biweekly</i> .		Your writer split the word for 'manna' into two words, but kept this word for 'southwards' as a single word, even though the latter only occurs twice in OHG. Is there any logic here, or just intuition, or some mix?

	<u>Word Initial, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Final</u>	<u>Word Final, Syl Final</u>
/lp/ Morphemic	Not Found	/a <u>lp</u> /+/o:n/	Not Found	Not Found
Assign stress		[á <u>lp</u>]+[o:n]		
Syllabification				
Raising				
Rounding				
Words assembled		[á <u>l</u> .po:n]		
Fronting				
V-Reduction				
Fortition				
Assimilation				
Epenthesis				
Lenition				
C-Reduction				
Elision				
Lowering				
Speech->Writing		<á <u>lp</u> ôn>		
Variation		<a <u>lp</u> on>		
Miniscule		similitudine ursi et muris . daz heizen uuir murem montis . \ in diên lochen dero alpôn \ uuanda iz in foraminibus alpium sína festi hábet .		
Etymology		ELat <Alpes>		
OHG lexeme		alpūn		
MHG lexeme		alpen		
Latin gloss		'Alpes'		
German gloss		'Alpen'		
English gloss		'Alps'		
Class		Noun wk (n)		
Inflection		fem gen pl		
Cititation		Np38414 : II, 438, 14		
Notes		Names for rivers and mountains and lakes can be very ancient. The Alps may derive from CLatin <i>albus</i> 'white', or maybe some Celtic word, or from an even older, forgotten language.		

	<u>Word Initial, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Final</u>	<u>Word Final, Syl Final</u>
/lv/ Morphemic	/žta <u>ll</u> /+/veh+u/	/wo <u>lv</u> +e/	/tswel <u>IF</u> +t+u/	/wo <u>lv</u> /
Assign stress	[žtá <u>ll</u>][+][véh+u]	[wó <u>lv</u> +e]	[tswé <u>IF</u> +t+u]	[wó <u>lv</u>]
Syllabification	[žtá <u>ll</u>][+][vé.hu]	[wó <u>lv</u> .e]	[tswé. <u>IF</u> .tu]	
Raising				
Rounding				
Words assembled	[žtá <u>ll</u> .vè.hu]			
Fronting				
V-Reduction			[tswé <u>l</u> əF.tu]	
Fortition	[štá <u>ll</u> .vè.hu]			
Assimilation				
Epenthesis				
Lenition				
C-Reduction	[štál.vè.hu]			
Elision			[tswé <u>l</u> F.tu]	
Lowering				
Speech->Writing	<stál <u>u</u> ého>	<uuó <u>l</u> ua>	<zué <u>l</u> fto>	<uuó <u>l</u> f>
Variation	<stál <u>f</u> ého>		<zeuué <u>l</u> fto>	<uuo <u>l</u> f>
Miniscule	uuanda er in_schérm ne-uuás . íro líbe \ ne- líbta er fone démo tóde . íro stá <u>lf</u> ého betéta er in demo tóde .	also herodem \ irslágenin áuuéisin fuhse unde uuó <u>l</u> ua \ CHRISTVS námnda . Alde íro occisa cadauera frézent uulpes et lupi .	Der ze-uué <u>l</u> fto gradus der \ ist infantum et innocentum . diè ne- darf eccllesia sámenôn . Mater gratia \ souget sie an íro arme .	Sezze íro fursten . Vuieo? Also du iü oreb \ dúrri uuó <u>l</u> f \ saxtost . der siccitas hèizzet . et zeb . der lupus heizzet .
Etymology	Gmc */stalla-/ , */fehu-/	Gmc */wulfa-/	Gmc */twalibi-/	Gmc */wulfa-/
OHG lexeme	stalfihu, 1	wolf, 28	zwelifto, 4	wolf, 28
MHG lexeme	Not Found	wolf	zwelif	wolf
Latin gloss	iumentum	'lupus'	'duodecimus'	'lupus'
German gloss	'Lasttier'	'Wolf'	'zwölfte'	'Wolf'
English gloss	'beast of burden'	'wolf'	'twelfth'	'wolf'
Class	Noun str (u)	Noun str (a)	Number Ordinal	Noun str (a)
Inflection	neut acc pl	masc nom pl	masc nom sg wk	masc nom sg
Citation	Np28309 : II, 319, 21	Np21318 : II, 238, 1	Np48306 : II, 546, 21	Np30503 : II, 345, 2
Notes	The major declensions for nouns in Notker were a/jə, ɔ/jō, and n (weak). But there are still relics of others from Germanic, like u here.	Your writer anchored a paper, SPN03, around the words for 'wolf' here and those for 'help' on the next page. Philology can both delight and feel trivial, sort of like crossword puzzles.	This is a weak example. The small, capital F, so /F/, marks either /f/ or /v/. Most scholars would just posit /f/ here. Also note that the elision does not match how other forms are handled.	Another spelling rule, where both [f] and [v] are written <f> word finally. Your writer has proposed this, in SPN03, but you should know that it is not the view of most scholars.

	<u>Word Initial, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Final</u>	<u>Word Final, Syl Final</u>
/lf/ Morphemic	Not Found	/h <u>el</u> f+e+nn+ɪ/	Not Found	/hi <u>l</u> f/
Assign stress		[h <u>el</u> f+e+nn+ɪ]		[hi <u>l</u> f]
Syllabification		[h <u>el</u> .fən.nɪ]		
Raising				
Rounding				
Words assembled				
Fronting				
V-Reduction		[h <u>el</u> .fən.nɪ]		
Fortition				
Assimilation				
Epenthesis				
Lenition				
C-Reduction				
Elision				
Lowering				
Speech->Writing		<h <u>el</u> fenne>		<hi <u>l</u> f>
Variation				
Miniscule		Tô chád sí is spûotigo uuésen ze_h <u>el</u> fenne . nio cillenius \ fône ueneris spénsten áber ferlúhter . únde níetig uuórtener .		Da pater ętherios menti \ conscendere cetus . Tú fater . hi <u>l</u> f mír hína ze_chómenne \ ze dero úf-mánigi .
Etymology		Gmc */helpa-/		Gmc */helpa-/
OHG lexeme		helfan, 198		helfan, 198
MHG lexeme		helfen		helfen
Latin gloss		'adiuvare'		'adiuvare'
German gloss		'helfen'		'helfen'
English gloss		'help'		'help'
Class		Verb: str (3), inf		Verb: str (3)
Inflection		neut dat sg		2nd sg imper
Citation		Nc04405 : I, 727, 10		Nc15707 : I, 718, 24
Notes	Benware writes that any syllable initial combination must also be able to occur word initially. If one accepts that, does [h <u>el</u> .fən.nɪ] imply that [f] could occur word initially after [l], even if there are no examples?	You can see infinitives ending with /nn/, which normally reduces to just [n], except when they are inflected, as here.		Ditto with word final and syllable final. Again, if one accepts Benware's statement, does [hi <u>l</u> f] imply that [lf] could occur syllable final, but word internal, even if we find no examples for the column to the left?

	<u>Word Initial, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Final</u>	<u>Word Final, Syl Final</u>
/lpf/ Morphemic	/gurt+il/+/pflég+u:n/	/wél(p)f+ɪr/	Not Found	/wél(p)f/
Assign stress	[gúrt+íll]+[pflég+u:n]	[wél(p)f+ɪr]		[wél(p)f]
Syllabification	[gúr.tíll]+[pflé.gu:n]	[wél.(p)fɪr]		
Raising				
Rounding				
Words assembled	[gúr.tíll.pflè.gu:n]			
Fronting	[gúr.tíll.pflè.gu:n]			
V-Reduction	[gúr.tríll.pflè.gu:n]	[wél.(p)fər]		
Fortition	[kúr.tríll.pflè.gu:n]			
Assimilation				
Epenthesis				
Lenition				
C-Reduction				
Elision				
Lowering				
Speech->Writing	<kúrtil flégûn>	<uuélfër>		<uuélf>
Variation	<cúrtil flégûn>			
Miniscule	Uuégoléittun . héim\bríngun . sálbsmíxun . cúrtilflégun . súln díh tódige díerna gebien\do zu ín lãdon . dáz tu íro ferte uuáltêst .	Ter áffo guúinnet ío zuéi uuélfër . únde déro zuéio . íst ímo daz éina liebera . dãnne daz ánder . Taz liebera chêret ío fúre síh !		târ uuírfet er ímo éi\na . sámó so ér ímo ergébe daz uuélf . In_déro ersíhet er síh . únde uuãnet taz píldé uuésen síh uuélf .
Etymology	Gmc */gurdila-/, */plega-/	Gmc */hwelpa-/		Gmc */hwelpa-/
OHG lexeme	gurtilpflega, 1	welpf, 24		welpf, 24
MHG lexeme	Not found	wēlp, wēlf		wēlp, wēlf
Latin gloss	'Cinxia, goddess of marriage'	'catulus'		'catulus'
German gloss	'Hüterin des Gürtels'	'Jungtier'		'Jungtier'
English gloss	'guardian of the belt'	'whelp'		'whelp'
Class	Noun wk (n)	Noun str (iz)		Noun str (iz)
Inflection	fem acc sg	neut acc pl		neut acc sg
Citation	Nc13409: I, 815, 15	Nb13804 : I, 164, 8		Nb13820 : I, 164, 26

Notes

Notker here is trying to explain Cinxia, the goddess of marriage, who guards the chastity belt of a maiden before her wedding.

Another weak example, the /lpf/ here could easily be just /lf/. Related to this question would be the Benrather Line and Rhenish Fan, both of which track the shifting of obstruents across German dialects.

That line and fan may show that one dialect has [ts] after [r] from an original */rt/, while another has [s] or even [t]. And the pattern in /rp/ or /rk/ may match or not.

After working through this document, what shifting would you posit for Notker? Will a preceding nasal differ from a preceding liquid? Will patterns hold across place of articulation (labial, dental, velar)?

	<u>Word Initial, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Final</u>	<u>Word Final, Syl Final</u>
/rb/ Morphemic	/ɪr ɪ balde:nn/	/ɪr+žtar ɪ +je+t/	/ɪr+žtar ɪ +/t+o:n/	/ɪr+žtar ɪ /
Assign stress	[ɪr ɪ bald+e:nn]	[ɪr+žtár ɪ +je+t]	[ɪr+žtár ɪ]+[t+o:n]	[ɪr+žtár ɪ]
Syllabification	[ɪr ɪ .bál.de:nn]	[ɪr.žtár ɪ .bjet]	[ɪr.žtár ɪ]+[to:n]	[ɪr.žtár ɪ]
Raising		[ɪr.žtär ɪ .bjet]		
Rounding				
Words assembled			[ɪr.žtár ɪ .to:n]	
Fronting				
V-Reduction	[ə ɪ .bál.de:nn]	[ə ɪ .žtär ɪ .bət]	[ə ɪ .žtár ɪ .to:n]	[ə ɪ .žtár ɪ]
Fortition		[ə ɪ .štär ɪ .bət]	[ə ɪ .štár ɪ .to:n]	[ə ɪ .štár ɪ]
Assimilation				
Epenthesis				
Lenition				
C-Reduction	[ə ɪ .bál.de:n]			
Elision				
Lowering				
Speech->Writing	<er ɪ baldēn>	<er stér ɪ bet>	<er stár ɪ btôn>	<er stár ɪ b>
Variation			<ir stár ɪ btôn>	
Miniscule	Únde iogeli\chen úbelen . úbeles síh erbaldēn ! fōne únengéltedo . únde dés \ fōlle- frúmigen dúrb lōn .	Tie ófto erstérbet . íoh táz \ sie fliegâ bizent . íoh táz éteuuáz ín sie uersklufet .	Κετρουóβτερ sliēf ih . Sie truóβton mih . so / filo iz ze ín_getráf . unde irstár ɪ btton mih . aber mir uuás iz slâf . / unde ráuuu .	únde sô ín paulus kefänge\nen ze_romo brâhta . uuio er ín_custodia erstár ɪ b . ún\de sîn sún úmbe ármhéit smídōn lírmeta .
Etymology	Gmc */balpa-/	Gmc */starbja-/	Gmc */starbja-/	Gmc */sterba-/
OHG lexeme	irbaldēn, 21	irsterben, 11	irsterben, 11	irsterban, 111
MHG lexeme	erbalden	ersterben	ersterben	ersterben
Latin gloss	'audere'	'necare'	'necare'	'mori'
German gloss	'kühn werden'	'töten'	'töten'	'zugrunde gehen'
English gloss	'become bold'	'kill'	'kill'	'perish'
Class	Verb wk (ē), inf	Verb wk (ja)	Verb wk (ja)	Verb str (3)
Inflection	uninflected	3rd sg pres	3rd pl past	3rd sg past
Citation	Nb03029 : I, 38, 1	Nx12345 : I, 104, 10	Np19419 : II, 215, 28	Nb05125 : I, 61, 30
Notes	Notker's weak verbs have a stem vowel, either je (1st class), ō (2nd class), or as here with ē (3rd class). Stems relate somewhat to meaning. So 'je' generally takes a past tense intransitive and makes it causative, where 'died' adapts to 'make died'.	Note how the infinitives [ə ɪ .štér ɪ .bən] 'perish' [ə ɪ .štär ɪ .bən] 'cause to perish' are both written <erstérben>. This is difficult for learners of standard German, where the /e/ and /ä/ have merged.	The stem vowels are not found in the dental preterite of weak verbs, nor often in the past participle (especially if inflected). How does Raising give us a clue here?	This is the strong verb, the source for the dental preterite with the /je/ stem vowel. As in Modern German, strong verbs mark different tenses by changing the vowel - <i>sterben</i> (<i>stirbt</i>), <i>starb</i> , <i>ist gestorben</i> . What form gets drawn into weak verbs?

	<u>Word Initial, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Final</u>	<u>Word Final, Syl Final</u>
/rp/ Morphemic	/abɪr/+/purpʊr/+/u:n/	/purpʊr/+/i:n+ɪn/	Not Found	Not Found
Assign stress	[áɪr̥]+[púr̥pʊr̥]+[u:n]	[púr̥pʊr̥]+[í:n+ɪn]		
Syllabification	[á.bɪr̥]+[púr̥.pʊr̥]+[u:n]	[púr̥.pʊr̥][í:.nɪn]		
Raising				
Rounding				
Words assembled	[á.bɪr̥.púr̥.pʊ.ru:n]	[púr̥.pʊ.rĩ:.nɪn]		
Fronting				
V-Reduction	[á.bər̥.púr̥.pʊ.ru:n]	[púr̥.pʊ.rɪ̃.nən]		
Fortition				
Assimilation				
Epenthesis				
Lenition				
C-Reduction				
Elision				
Lowering				
Speech->Writing	<áber_púrpurûn>	<púrpurinen>		
Variation	<áber_púrpúrûn>	<púrpurînen>		
Miniscule	Sô man áber_púrpúrûn \ máchôn uuíle . sô súochet man díu animalia ín_demo mére . \ díu latine conchilia héizent .	Jóh minerua díu \ máged . cáreta daz mágeti mít íro smócchen . ába-genómene\ro spénelun . únde mít íro púrpurînen gúrtele .		
Etymology	ELat <purpura>	ELat <purpureus>		
OHG lexeme	purpura, 8	purpurīn, 8		
MHG lexeme	purpur	purpurīn		
Latin gloss	'purpura'	'purpureus'		
German gloss	'Purpur'	'purpurrot'		
English gloss	'purple'	'purple'		
Class	Noun wk (n).	Adj.		
Inflection	fem acc sg	masc dat sg wk		
Citattation	Nb08406 : I, 97, 9	Nx01217 : I, 697, 30		
Notes	Colors are fascinating, as the palettes are different across languages and cultures. For example, in the four horsemen of the Apocalypse, our pale horse may have had some light green to it, or at least in the original Koine Greek of the New Testament.	Even just look at the English and German glosses here - 'purple' vs 'purple-red'. What is crimson then, or violet, in Modern German or Old Alemannic?	Did writer mis-analyze the <î> in <púrpurînen>? We talk about stress later. But if this was secondary, rather than tertiary stress, the vowel would have remained long.	

	<u>Word Initial, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Final</u>	<u>Word Final, Syl Final</u>
/rv/ Morphemic	/xeller+vas/	Not Found	Not Found	Not Found
Assign stress	[xéller+vàs]			
Syllabification	[xél.lər.vàs]			
Raising				
Rounding				
Words assembled				
Fronting				
V-Reduction	[xél.lər.vàs]			
Fortition				
Assimilation				
Epenthesis				
Lenition				
C-Reduction	[xél.lər.vàs]			
Elision				
Lowering				
Speech->Writing	<chéller <u>u</u> áz>			
Variation	<chéllir <u>f</u> áz>			
Miniscule	unde dannan uerdent li\quati in Gotes chéllir- f áz des cháliuuin sune chrucis chint des\ ke-chriuzegotin chint . \ in apothecas dei .			
Etymology	CLat <cellarium>, Gmc */fata-/			
OHG lexeme	kellarfaz, 2			
MHG lexeme	Not found			
Latin gloss	'apotheca, dolium vinum'			
German gloss	'Weinfass'			
English gloss	'wine cask'			
Class	Noun str (a)			
Inflection	neut acc pl			
Citation	Np30615 : II, 346, 23			
Notes	Wine would have been a luxury to Notker's students, and a cask of wine quite a treasure. The beer was different than ours nowadays, maybe sweeter, as it did not contain hops. And the goal of fermentation was less intoxication than water purification.	That <c> in CLatin <cellarium> comes across as an /x/ here in [xél.lər]. How would it come across if the word had been just borrowed in Notker's day, so from his ELatin?		

	<u>Word Initial, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Final</u>	<u>Word Final, Syl Final</u>
/rf/ Morphemic	Not Found	/gɪ+worf+n/	/bɪ+dorf/+/t+e/	/bɪ+darf/
Assign stress		[gɪ+wórf+n]	[bɪ+dórf]+[t+e]	[bɪ+dárf]
Syllabification		[gɪ.wór.fən]	[bɪ.dórf]+[te]	[bɪ.dárf]
Raising				
Rounding				
Words assembled			[bɪ.dórf.te]	
Fronting				
V-Reduction				
Fortition				
Assimilation				
Epenthesis				
Lenition				
C-Reduction				
Elision				[pɪ.dárf]
Lowering				
Speech->Writing		<ge uuórfen>	<be dórfta>	<pe dárf>
Variation				
Miniscule		uuán\da dér únstâte íst . únde úngeuuáltig sîn sêlbes . pediu há\bet er hína geuuórfen den skilt . dáz chît tes múotes fēsti .	únde mísse námigiu . i . dī\uersiuoca . ut ignis lapis color . Ziu uer\suigeta er déro? Téro nebedórfra er . ze_disemo búoche .	Táz íst argumentum a simili . Uuánda álsó corpus pedárf medicine . só bedárf\ óuh anima .
Etymology		Gmc */werpa-/ werfan, 91 wērfen	Gmc */þerba-/ bidurfan, 50 bedürfen	Gmc */þerba-/ bidurfan, 50 bedürfen
OHG lexeme				
MHG lexeme				
Latin gloss		'iacere'	'indigere'	'indigere'
German gloss		'werfen'	'bedürfen'	'bedürfen'
English gloss		'throw'	'need'	'need'
Class		Verb str (3), past part	Verb pret-pres	Verb pret-pres
Inflection		uninflected	3rd sg past	3rd sg pres
Citattation		Nb01826 : I, 22, 30	Nk00901 : I, 371, 19	Nb20712 : I, 265, 18
Notes		Note the past participle of just /n/ for strong verbs. Also posited is a stem vowel of /e/ for strong verbs too, a convention that works in Notker, but probably not in earlier Germanic languages.	A preterite-present verb gets its name because it forms its present test off the past (preterite) form of a strong verb, and then forms a new past tense with the dental preterite.	Many grammatical terms overlap, so preterite = past, gerund = present participle, and your writer has seen subjunctive glossed as exhortative, conditional, and even conjunctive (from the Latin and German terms).

	<u>Word Initial, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Final</u>	<u>Word Final, Syl Final</u>
/rpf/ Morphemic	/tsiter ₊ /p _f in/	/har(p)f+u:n/	Not Found	Not Found
Assign stress	[tsíter ₊][p _f ín]	[hárp(p)f+u:n]		
Syllabification	[tsí.tər ₊].[p _f ín]	[hárp ₊ .(p)fu:n]		
Raising				
Rounding				
Words assembled	[tsí.tər.p _f ín]			
Fronting				
V-Reduction	[tsí.tər.p _f ín]			
Fortition				
Assimilation				
Epenthesis				
Lenition				
C-Reduction				
Elision				
Lowering				
Speech->Writing	<zíter ₊ fín>	<hárfûn>		
Variation	<zíter ₊ fin>	<hárfun>		
Miniscule	nouit fidis et sacrum plectrum sonare \ treicium carmen . Dir irdénchentero . chán der séito . únde daz zíter ₊ \fin sínge in _traciskun .	Deinde barbito aurataque cheli . ac doctis fidibus personare . Únde mêister\lichó sínge . an hárfun . iób an lýrun .		
Etymology	Elat <cithara>, Gmc */penna-/	Gmc */harp(p)ō-/		
OHG lexeme	zitarpfin, 1	harpfa, 40		
MHG lexeme	Not found	harpfe		
Latin gloss	'plectrum'	'cithara'		
German gloss	'Zither, Pflock'	'Harfe'		
English gloss	'zither pick'	'harp'		
Class	Noun str (a)	Noun wk (n)		
Inflection	masc nom sg	fem dat sg		
Citation	Nc12345 : I, 791, 21	Nc04504 : I, 728, 6		
Notes	Here is a ELatin (or VLatin, originally Greek?) word for 'harp', and next a Germanic one. And English now has both <i>zither</i> plus <i>harp</i> plus <i>guitar</i> . Can you trace how the first and third could be related, if borrowed out at different stages of Latin?	Another form for 'harp' is spelled <hárfhôn>. And <ph> marks [pf] in <ópfer> 'sacrifice' two dozen times, as <ópher>. Given that, should <rph> be the standard spelling here, and <rf> a variation?	Now that you've seen words for 'whelp' and 'harp', how do you start drawing a Rhenish Fan for Notker. Will that same pattern extend to the dentals and velars?	Or is Notker's word for 'harp' borrowed from some other OHG dialect? And so maybe an /rpf/ here has nothing to do with the history of Old Alemannic, but is just what some foreign musician once grunted when pointing at his instrument?

	<u>Word Initial, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Final</u>	<u>Word Final, Syl Final</u>
/nb/ Morphemic	/u <u>n</u> + <u>b</u> ir+i:g+u:n/	/la <u>n</u> b+ir/	/g <u>ɪ</u> +xru <u>n</u> b+t+ <u>ɪ</u> /	/la <u>n</u> b/
Assign stress	[ú <u>n</u> + <u>b</u> ir+i:g+u:n]	[lá <u>n</u> b+ir]	[g <u>ɪ</u> +xru <u>n</u> b+t+ <u>ɪ</u>]	[lá <u>n</u> b]
Syllabification	[ú <u>n</u> . <u>b</u> i.rĩ:.gu:n]	[lá <u>n</u> . <u>b</u> +ir]	[g <u>ɪ</u> .xru <u>n</u> b.t <u>ɪ</u>]	
Raising		[lǎ <u>n</u> . <u>b</u> +ir]		
Rounding				
Words assembled				
Fronting				
V-Reduction	[ú <u>n</u> . <u>b</u> i.rĩ.gu:n]	[lǎ <u>n</u> . <u>b</u> ər]		
Fortition				
Assimilation	[ú <u>m</u> . <u>b</u> i.rĩ.gu:n]	[lǎ <u>m</u> . <u>b</u> ər]	[g <u>ɪ</u> .xru <u>m</u> b.t <u>ɪ</u>]	
Epenthesis				
Lenition				
C-Reduction			[g <u>ɪ</u> .xru <u>m</u> b.t <u>ɪ</u>]	
Elision				
Lowering				
Speech->Writing	<ú <u>m</u> <u>b</u> irigû>	<l <u>é</u> mber>	<ge chrú <u>m</u> bte>	<l <u>á</u> mb>
Variation	<ú <u>m</u> <u>b</u> irigû>		<ge chrú <u>m</u> pte>	
Miniscule	Qui habitare facit ste\rilem in domo . matrem filiorum letantem . Der dié ú <u>m</u> birigun . al\so \ diu ecclesia uuás ér iro sponsus châme .	unde íro posteriores fone diên gescriben \ ist . AFFERTE DOMINO FILIOS ARIETVM . die fréuton sib \ also l <u>é</u> mber .	áalso diu érda íst in \ aprili . só diu súnna gât in ariete . Án arietis hórnen stânt filo glá\te stérnen fiere . nâh tien hórnen gechrú <u>m</u> pte .	Diú fóre-zêichenunga íst \ l <u>á</u> mb fone hértó hína . diu uuârhêit íst chómen . Agnus de grege uuard er ge-óphe\rót .
Etymology	Gmc */beriga-/	Gmc */lamba-/	Gmc */krumbja-/	Gmc */lamba-/
OHG lexeme	unbirīg, 7	lamb, 33	gikrumben, 5	lamb, 33
MHG lexeme	unbirec	lam, lamp	krum-, krump-	lam, lamp
Latin gloss	'sterilis'	'agnus'	'intorquere'	'agnus'
German gloss	'unfruchtbar'	'Lamm'	'verdrehen'	'Lamm'
English gloss	'barren'	'lamb'	'twist'	'lamb'
Class	Adj	Noun str (iz)	Verb wk (ja), past part	Noun str (iz)
Inflection	fem acc sg wk	neut nom pl	masc nom pl	neut nom sg
Citation	Np42511 : II, 485, 8	Np42606 : II, 486, 6	Nc06604 : I, 750, 23	Np13512 : II, 146, 20
Notes	See the Germanic */beriga-/, so the original /e/ as in verb <béren> 'carry'. The first /i/ in <bírīg> 'fertile' marks a much older vowel height harmony: raising of short /e/ to /i/ before /i,u/, and lowering of /i,u/ to /e,o/ before /a/.	Note that [ú <u>m</u> . <u>b</u> i.rĩ.gu:n] is not fronted. Your writer has linked fronting to gradations - of both the palatization and juncture of the following high, front (semi)vowel.	Your writer sees this [ɪ] as not palatized enough to front /u/ in [g <u>ɪ</u> .xru <u>m</u> b.t <u>ɪ</u>], and the stressed /i/ as not joined tightly enough to front the /u/ in [ú <u>m</u> . <u>b</u> i.rĩ.gu:n].	The stops after nasals are pronounced, in <l <u>á</u> mb> and <g <u>á</u> ng>, unlike in English <i>lamb</i> and <i>gang</i> . We can tell this because <mb> and <ng> do not inhibit Anlautgesetz.

	<u>Word Initial, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Final</u>	<u>Word Final, Syl Final</u>
/np/ Morphemic	/tiwr+ižɾ+u:n/+/purpʊr/+/u:n/	/tɪnpɛn/+/u:n/	Not Found	Not Found
Assign stress	[tɪwr+ižɾ+u:n]+[púrɸʊr]+[u:n]	[tɪnpɛn]+[u:n]		
Syllabification	[tɪw.rɪ.žɾu:n]+[púr.ɸʊr]+[u:n]	[tɪn.pɛn]+[u:n]		
Raising				
Rounding	[tú:.rɪ.žɾu:n]+[púr.ɸʊr]+[u:n]			
Words assembled	[tú:.rɪ.žɾu:n.púr.ɸʊ.ru:n]	[tɪn.pɛ.nu:n]		
Fronting				
V-Reduction	[tú:.rɪ.žɾu:n.púr.ɸʊ.ru:n]			
Fortition	[tú:.rɪ.ʃtu:n.púr.ɸʊ.ru:n]			
Assimilation	[tú:.rɪ.ʃtu:m.púr.ɸʊ.ru:n]	[tɪm.pɛ.nu:n]		
Epenthesis				
Lenition				
C-Reduction				
Elision				
Lowering				
Speech->Writing	<tíurestûn_púrpurûn>	<tímpanûn>		
Variation		<timpanun>		
Miniscule	Tóh tér grímmo únde dér zúrlústígo nero síh úbermûotlí\cho gáretî . mít tero tíurestûn púrpurûn . únde mít scô\nên gímmôn .	Sî ín dero zéseuuun den blíg hábende . únde án dero uuínsterun \ éina tímpanun mít prútelichen chláfleichen .		
Etymology	ELat <purpura>	Elat <tympanum>		
OHG lexeme	purpura, 8	timpana, 2		
MHG lexeme	purpur	Not found		
Latin gloss	'purpura'	'tympanum'		
German gloss	'Purpur'	'Handpauke'		
English gloss	'purple'	'tambourine'		
Class	Noun wk (n)	Noun wk (n)		
Inflection	fem gen sg	fem acc sg		
Citation	Nb12918 : I, 167, 24	Nc05907 : I, 743, 23		
Notes	What a mess. The longer the phrase, the more sound changes it seems to trip into. Note that your writer allows processes that cross syllable boundaries to also cross word boundaries. So the dental [n] moves to a labial [m] before the labial [p].	English <i>timpani</i> is really a plural, a set of kettledrums, originally from a Greek word for 'strike', related (through French) to English <i>timbre</i> . Words for instruments likely traveled with their musicians.		

	<u>Word Initial, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Final</u>	<u>Word Final, Syl Final</u>
/NV/ Morphemic	/hejm/+/vuer/+/t+e/	/viNV+I/	/viNV+t+e/	/viNV/
Assign stress	[hɛjm]+[vúɛr]+[t+ɐ]	[vɪNV+I]	[vɪNV+t+ɐ]	[vɪNV]
Syllabification	[hɛjm]+[vúɛr]+[tɐ]	[vɪN.VI]	[vɪNV.tɐ]	
Raising	[hǎjm]+[vúɛr]+[tɐ]			
Rounding		[vún.VI]	[vúnv.tɐ]	[vúnv]
Words assembled	[hǎjm.vúɛr.tɐ]			
Fronting				
V-Reduction				
Fortition			[fúnv.tɐ]	[fúnv]
Assimilation		[vúm.VI]	[fúm.v.tɐ]	[fúmv]
Epenthesis				
Lenition				
C-Reduction				
Elision				
Lowering				
Speech->Writing	<héim fûorta>	<uínue>	<fínfta>	<fínf>
Variation		<fínue>	<fímfta>	
Miniscule	uuio alexander paris filius priami . spartam ciuitatem \ greçiɛ eruáht . únde helenam . uxorem regis menelai ímo ábuuertígemo \ nám . únde héim fûorta ze troio .	Úbe finf summa bona \ uuârin . sô uuârin óuh finf beatitudines . sô uuârin óuh tero uuúrche\dôn finue . uuânda iogelichiu dúrh síh beatum uuórh̄ti .	mít uuíu gót tia uuérht ríhte . dáz íst \ taz fimfta . únde uuânest tia uuéhsela dero uuílsáldôn \ tuárôn âne ríhtare . dáz íst taz séhsta .	sô uuârin óuh finf beatitudines . sô uuârin óuh tero uuúrche\dôn finue . uuânda iogelichiu dúrh síh beatum uuórh̄ti .
Etymology	Gmc */haima-/, */fōrja-/	Gmc */femf-/	Gmc */femftō-/	Gmc */femf-/
OHG lexeme	heimfuoren, 1	fimf	fimfto	fimf
MHG lexeme	Not found	vünf	vünfte	vünf
Latin gloss	'ducere domum'	'quinque'	'quintus'	'quinque'
German gloss	'heimführen'	'fünf'	'fünfte'	'fünf'
English gloss	'lead home'	'five'	'fifth'	'five'
Class	Verb: wk (ja).	Number Cardinal.	Number Ordinal.	Number Cardinal.
Inflection	3rd sg past	fem nom pl	nom sg neut wk	uninflected
Citation	Nb22728 : I, 298, 2	Nb16420 : I, 197, 29	Nb03918 : I, 48, 25	Nb16419 : I, 197, 28
Notes	Notker's goal was teaching. So his Latin is generally easy, and glossed with Old Alemannic forms. The result are texts that are quite approachable to students of German, especially if they had some Spanish in high school.	You can see here the alternation between <nu> word medially and <nf> word finally, a pattern that your writer believes marked [mv] from /nv/ in both cases. The small, capital /N/ denotes 'any nasal'.	For /nf/, which via assimilation and epenthesis would beocme [mpf], your writer posits the spelling <mf>, both word internal and final. But this is /nv/ in <fímfta>.	Do we have a fortition on the left, where the following [tɐ] in [fúmv.tɐ] generates [fúmpf.tɐ]? Is that why it is <mf> in <fímfta> but <nf> in <fínf>? A curse of philology is that you see patterns everywhere, and often they conflict.

	<u>Word Initial, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Final</u>	<u>Word Final, Syl Final</u>
/nf/ Morphemic	/aF _{Tr} Ir+In ₊ /+f _{UN} TEMINTT/	/un+gI+lIn(p)f+j+iw/	/un+žaN(p)F _T +j+ir+u/	/gI+lAn(p)f/
Assign stress	[áF _{Tr} Ir+In ₊]+[f _{UN} TEMINTT]	[ún+gI+lIn(p)f+j+iw]	[ún+žàN(p)F _T +j+ir+u]	[gI+lán(p)f]
Syllabification	[áF.ɪ.rIn ₊]+[f _{UN} .tE.mINTT]	[ún.gI.lIn.(p)fjiw]	[ún.žàN(p)F.ɪjĩ.ru]	[gI.lán(p)f]
Raising			[ún.žän(p)F.ɪjĩ.ru]	
Rounding		[ún.gI.lIn.(p)fjü:]		
Words assembled	[áF.ɪ.rIn.f _{UN} .tE.mINTT]			
Fronting				
V-Reduction	[áF.ɪ.rən.f _{UN} .tE.məNTT]	[ún.gI.lIn.(p)fjü:]	[ún.žän(p)F.ɪĩ.ru]	
Fortition	[áF.ɪ.rən.f _{UN} .tE.məNTt]		[ún.žän(p)(v,f).ɪĩ.ru]	
Assimilation	[áF.ɪ.rəm.f _{UN} .tE.məNTt]	[ún.gI.lIm.(p)fjü:]	[ún.žäm(p)(v,f).ɪĩ.ru]	[gI.lám(p)f]
Epenthesis	[áF.ɪ.rəm.pf _{UN} .tE.məNTt]	[ún.gI.lIm.pfjü:]	[ún.žäm(v,pf).ɪĩ.ru]	[gI.lámpf]
Lenition	[áF.ɪ.rəm.pf _{UN} .de.məNTt]			
C-Reduction	[áF.ɪ.rəm.pf _{UN} .de.mənt]			
Elision				
Lowering				
Speech->Writing	<áfteren fúndament>	<ún ge límf <u>i</u> u>	<ún sémf <u>t</u> ero>	<ge lám <u>f</u> >
Variation	<áfterin fúndament>	<ún ge límp <u>h</u> iu>		
Miniscule	Tes êrerin úber-zímber . \ uuírdit tes áfterin fúndament . álde des êrer[er]in fún\dament uuírdit tes áfterin úber-zímber	multa inconuenientia erunt . Sol man dax \ samint spréchen . dax súndero uuár ist . so uuér\dent târ uz manigiu gechôse úngelimp <u>h</u> iu .	Du scírmest mih . sie scír\met iro lúg . Mít demo ántseídon't sie sib iro súndôn . der \ ist únsémf <u>t</u> ero ze findenne danne diû uuárhêit .	Pe_díu ne ge\lím <u>f</u> et níeht sáment . taz súnderigo gelám <u>f</u> . \ Neque homo . homo animal . uel bipes . Nob sús ketân \ conpositio ne tóug .
Etymology	ELat <fundamentum>	Gmc */galempj-/	Gmc */sambja-/	Gmc */galempa-/
OHG lexeme	fundament, 14	ungilimpfi, 4	unsemfti, 44	gilimpfan, 54
MHG lexeme	fundamënt	ungelimpfe	unsenfte	gelimpfen
Latin gloss	'fundamentum'	'inconueniens'	'difficilis'	'competere'
German gloss	'Grundlage'	'unangemessen'	'schwer'	'angemessen sein'
English gloss	'foundation'	'inappropriate'	'difficult'	'be appropriate'
Class	Noun str (a)	Adj (j)	Adj (j)	Verb str (3)
Inflection	neut nom sg	neut nom pl	masc nom sg comp wk	3rd sg past
Citattation	Ns02913 : I, 598, 25	Ni20601 : I, 552, 26	Ps51607 : II, 582, 18	Ni12345 : I, 556, 5
Notes	It is a strict following of 'Posit as Little as Possible' in SPN01 that leads <áfter> to be posited with either an [f] or [v], [áF.tIr]. Should we replace /Ir/ with /ir/ for the comparative 'more aft', or was this reanalyzed by Notker as a single morpheme?	Again on the left, what would /ir/ vs [Ir] have done to the preceding /a/ in *[áF _{Tr} Ir]? How would <áfter> then be spelled? Or maybe /F _{Tr} / blocks that change, or /i/ is not palatal enough, or the combination?	Across this page, you are seeing raising of /a/ to /ä/, plus that earlier raising of /e/ to /i/, and even rounding of /iw/ to /ü:/, which will merge with the /u:/ that is fronted to /ü:/.	On these last three, your writer has <mf> marking [mpf], where <nf> marks [mv]. Also, revisit <áfter> now that you have seen <sémf <u>t</u> er>. Does /F _T / block fronting? If not, does the <er> in both words mark different vowels? Or is the issue the <m>?

	<u>Word Initial, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Final</u>	<u>Word Final, Syl Final</u>
/npf/ Morphemic	/INT+pflég+e+NT/	Not Found	Not Found	Not Found
Assign stress	[INT+pflég+e+NT]			
Syllabification	[INT.pflé.gəNT]			
Raising				
Rounding				
Words assembled				
Fronting				
V-Reduction	[əNT.pflé.gəNT]			
Fortition				
Assimilation	[əNT.pflé.gəNT]			
Epenthesis				
Lenition				
C-Reduction				
Elision				
Lowering				
Speech->Writing	<in flégent>			
Variation	<in phlégent>			
Miniscule	Óbe diēn sixzent spiritalēs . sanctę episcoporum animę inphlégent \ íro . úzzer steînen spréchant siē . daz siē hábent fōne prophetis \ et apostolis nals fōne platone .			
Etymology	Gmc */plega-/			
OHG lexeme	inpflegan			
MHG lexeme	enpflegen			
Latin gloss	'curare'			
German gloss	'sorgen für'			
English gloss	'care for'			
Class	Verb: st (5)			
Inflection	3rd sg pres			
Citation	Np38215 : II, 436, 5			

Notes
As in section /rf/ with *harp*, here we have <ph> marking [pf]. Notker obviously struggled with what letters to use for Old Alemannic.

Could the forms for /nf/ also get listed here, given Epenthesis? If so, will that also be the case the dentals and velars too, so /ns/ and /nx/?

Compare <únsémf^utero> with its cognate *so^ut*, and <fínf> with its cognate *fi^uve*. In English, we have an Ingvaeonic Spirant Law. What did it do? Compare German *Mund* with English *mou^uth*.

	<u>Word Initial, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Final</u>	<u>Word Final, Syl Final</u>
/Vd/ Morphemic	/ts <u>ue</u> +diēs+e+N <u>TT</u> +In/	/Ir+to <u>:d</u> +je+N <u>T</u> +u/	/Ir+to <u>:d</u> /+/t+i:/	/žk <u>ANT</u> /+/to <u>:d</u> /
Assign stress	[ts <u>úe</u> +diēs+e+N <u>TT</u> +In]	[Ir+t <u>ó</u> :d+je+N <u>T</u> +u]	[Ir+t <u>ó</u> :d]+[t+i:]	[ž <u>k</u> Á <u>N</u> T]+[t <u>ó</u> :d]
Syllabification	[ts <u>úe</u> . <u>d</u> iē.s <u>ə</u> NT. <u>T</u> In]	[Ir.t <u>ó</u> : <u>d</u> jeN. <u>T</u> u]	[Ir.t <u>ó</u> :d]+[ti:]	
Raising				
Rounding				
Words assembled			[Ir.t <u>ó</u> :d.ti:]	[ž <u>k</u> Á <u>N</u> T.t <u>ò</u> :d]
Fronting		[Ir.t <u>ö</u> : <u>d</u> jeN. <u>T</u> u]	[Ir+t <u>ö</u> :d.ti:]	
V-Reduction	[ts <u>úe</u> . <u>d</u> iē.s <u>ə</u> NT. <u>T</u> ən]	[ə.r.t <u>ö</u> : <u>d</u> əN. <u>T</u> u]	[ə.r.t <u>ö</u> :d.ti:]	
Fortition	[ts <u>úe</u> . <u>d</u> iē.s <u>ə</u> NT. <u>t</u> ən]			[š <u>k</u> Á <u>N</u> T.t <u>ò</u> :d]
Assimilation	[ts <u>úe</u> . <u>d</u> iē.s <u>ə</u> NT. <u>t</u> ən]	[ə.r.t <u>ö</u> : <u>d</u> əN. <u>T</u> u]		[š <u>k</u> Á <u>N</u> T.t <u>ò</u> :d]
Epenthesis				
Lenition		[ə.r.t <u>ö</u> : <u>d</u> əN. <u>d</u> u]		
C-Reduction				
Elision				
Lowering				
Speech->Writing	<z <u>û</u> o diēz <u>e</u> nten>	<er t <u>ô</u> d <u>e</u> ndo>	<er t <u>ô</u> t <u>î</u> >	<sc <u>á</u> nt t <u>ô</u> d>
Variation	<z <u>uo</u> diēz <u>z</u> enten>	<ir t <u>ô</u> d <u>e</u> ndo>	<ir t <u>ô</u> t <u>î</u> >	
Miniscule	Eripe me et libera me de \ aquis multis . Lôse mih fone uuazzeren manigen . fone <u>zuo</u> \ diēz <u>z</u> enten genuogen .	Adipem suum concluderunt . Vnde beslúzen \ íro spint . Daz chít . fóllemáston sih íro únrehtes . mih irt <u>ô</u> d <u>e</u> ndo .	Sol íz nâh ánderen chéden mortificare . sô íst daz \ daz er in irt <u>ô</u> t <u>î</u> \ ut mortificareret .	unde íh fone diû solti \ tod chrucis sc <u>á</u> nt- t <u>ô</u> d \ líden mortem . unde íoh mortem crucis .
Etymology	Gmc */peuta-/	Gmc */daupja-/	Gmc */daupja-/	Gmc */skanda-/, */daupu-/
OHG lexeme	zuodiozan, 3	irtôden, 5	irtôden, 5	skanttôd, 1
MHG lexeme	diezen	ertæten	ertæten	schande, tôt
Latin gloss	'affluere'	'tradere morti '	'tradere morti '	'mors crucis'
German gloss	'zufließen'	'dem Tod ausliefern'	'dem Tod ausliefern'	'schändlicher Tod'
English gloss	'flow towards'	'deliver to death'	'deliver to death'	'shameful death'
Class	Verb str (2), pres part	Verb wk (ja), pres part	Verb wk (ja)	Noun str (a)
Inflection	neut dat pl	neut gen pl (adv)	3rd sg past subj	masc acc sg
Citation	Np12345 : II, 590, 17	Np04613 : II, 45, 17	Np41301 : II, 471, 20	Np32006 : II, 362, 21
Notes	Here and to the right are two present participles that end differently. This one ends as /e+N <u>TT</u> +In/ [ə <u>NT</u> . <u>t</u> ən] <en <u>t</u> en>, while the next is /je+N <u>T</u> +u/ [ə <u>n</u> . <u>d</u> u] <en <u>d</u> o>. Historically, the present participle declined as a ja/jō adjective.	Most cases had a /j/ (ex: dat. pl. to the left), which geminated (doubled) the /t/. Yet some cases had no /j/, like here (gen pl), so just a single /t/. Why is this difference so noticeable in Notker?	Can this <t <u>ô</u> t <u>î</u> >, when compared to <sp <u>ât</u> t <u>e</u> n> (next page), argue against that fortition considered with <f <u>ím</u> f <u>t</u> a>? Could the <t#tt> contrast mark [d.t#t.t]?	In the OHG monophthongization, Germanic */ai, au/ become /e:/, /o:/, but in puzzling (and slightly different) environments. For */au/ to /o:/ like in */daupu-/ <t <u>ô</u> d>, the change is triggered before /r/, /h/, all dentals, and syllable finally.

	<u>Word Initial, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Final</u>	<u>Word Final, Syl Final</u>
/Vt/ Morphemic	/gɪ+trɛn(k)x+je+nn/	/ʒpa:t+o:r/	/gɪ+ʒpa:t+t+ɪn/	/tsɪ+ʒam+en+ɪ+gɪ+vueg+je+t/
Assign stress	[gɪ+trán(k)x+je+nn]	[ʒpá:t+ö:r]	[gɪ+ʒpá:t+t+ɪn]	[tsɪ+ʒám+en+ɪ+gɪ+vùeg+je+t]
Syllabification	[gɪ.trán.(k)xjenn]	[ʒpá:.tö:r]	[gɪ.ʒpá:t.tɪn]	[tsɪ.ʒá.me.nɪ.gɪ.vùe.gjet]
Raising	[gɪ.trǎn.(k)xjenn]			
Rounding				
Words assembled				
Fronting				[tsɪ.ʒá.me.nɪ.gɪ.vùe.gjet]
V-Reduction	[gɪ.trǎn.(k)xənn]	[ʒpá:.tö:r]	[gɪ.ʒpá:t.tən]	[tsɪ.ʒá.me.nɪ.gɪ.vùe.gət]
Fortition		[špá:.tö:r]	[gɪ.špá:t.tən]	
Assimilation	[gɪ.trǎŋ.(k)xənn]			
Epenthesis	[gɪ.trǎŋ(k).(k)xənn]			
Lenition				
C-Reduction	[gɪ.trǎŋk.xən]			
Elision				
Lowering				
Speech->Writing	<ge trénchen>	<spâtôr>	<ge spâttén>	<ze sámene ge fûoget>
Variation				
Miniscule	bediu stûont er dúrstegeêr . ín_demo uuázere . \ únde nemáhta síh is tóh nio ge <trénchen .<br=""></trénchen> Tér gótes chórot . témo \ nesól báz keskében .	sô er dia bréiti des signiferi ze_ferro begrífet . únde er des-te spâtor \ diu zéichen dúrh-kât . tóh er gâhoe .	úmbe trâgheit síh lichesoti inequalem . dáz chít únebenfértigen . \ únde fone diu gespâttén . Sín stérno neíst tânne nieht ébenfertig .	uuánda síu fûoget íro téil zú geméinero márcho . táz chít \ íro téil uuérdent zesámene gefûoget . mít \ keméinero márcho .
Etymology	Gmc */drankja-/	Gmc */spēdja-/	Gmc */spēdja-/	Gmc */fōgja-/
OHG lexeme	gitrenken, 13	spāti/spāto, adj/adv 25/16	spāten, 1	zisamanefuogen, 8
MHG lexeme	trenken	spæte/spāte, adj/adv	spāten	zesamenevüegen
Latin gloss	'reficere'	'tardus/tarde'	'morari'	'conectere'
German gloss	'zu trinken geben'	'spät'	'sich verspäten'	'verknüpfen'
English gloss	'refresh (with water)'	'late'	'be late'	'connect'
Class	Verb wk (ja), inf	Adj (j)	Verb wk (ja), past part	Verb: wk (ja), past part
Inflection	uninflected	gen pl comp (adv)	masc acc sg	uninflected
Citation	Nb18030 : I, 224, 11	Nc04517 : I, 728, 25	Nc04516 : I, 728, 23	Nk04713 : 'I, 405, 24
Notes	In standard German, you easily recognize the link between the strong verb <i>trinken</i> and it's corresponding weak ja-class <i>tränken</i> . In English, the links are a little harder - <i>drink/drench</i> , <i>stink/stench</i> , but also <i>bind/bend</i> .	Here we list both the adjective form and adverb form in both the OHG and the MHG lines, but only one form in the Germanic and Modern German lines. Which form is it?	Here we have that [t.t] potentially contrasting with [d.t] above. Unfortunately, your writer cannot find additional examples (after long vowels) to confirm or refute.	So again, how would any contrast in the left column affect our thoughts on <fímfta> instead of the expected <fínfta>, or say <gechrúmp ^t e> instead of <gechrúmb ^t e> (from <chrúmben>)? There may be no easy answer here, which is often the case in philology.

	<u>Word Initial, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Final</u>	<u>Word Final, Syl Final</u>
/Vž/ Morphemic	/vor+ <u>I</u> +žew+n+iw/	/gr <u>á</u> ž+I/	/xu <u>ž</u> +jɛ+NɪTɪ+I/	/gr <u>á</u> ž/
Assign stress	[vór+ <u>I</u> +žèw+n+iw]	[gr <u>á</u> ž+I]	[xú <u>ž</u> +jɛ+NɪTɪ+I]	[gr <u>á</u> ž]
Syllabification	[vó.r <u>I</u> .žèw.niw]	[gr <u>á</u> .žI]	[xú <u>ž</u> .žjɛNɪTɪ]	
Raising				
Rounding	[vó.r <u>I</u> .žõ:.nü:]			
Words assembled				
Fronting			[xú <u>ž</u> .žjɛNɪTɪ]	
V-Reduction			[xú <u>ž</u> .žəNɪTɪ]	
Fortition	[fó.r <u>I</u> .žõ:.nü:]		[xú <u>ž</u> .šəNɪTɪ]	
Assimilation			[xú <u>ž</u> .šəNɪTɪ]	
Epenthesis				
Lenition				
C-Reduction				
Elision				
Lowering				
Speech->Writing	<fóre <u>sé</u> uniu>	<gr <u>á</u> se>	<chú <u>s</u> sente>	<gr <u>á</u> s>
Variation				
Miniscule	uel ab deo prouiderifutura \ . uel euenire prouisa . Nû ist áber beidero nôT . ióh kót fóre séhen chúmftigiu . \ ióh fóre <u>sé</u> uniu geskéhen .	Somnos dáβατ herba salubres . Tie liute slifen dô \ héilesamo án demo gr <u>á</u> se . sie nehábetôn féderbétte .	Dû chûre in geometria . uuîo drî réixa grêh\te . án dien órten síh chússente . triangulum máchont . Et \ quid torqueat circulus .	Tér ist kegében tauro únde ma\io . uuánda danne íst lóub únde gr <u>á</u> s ín alegrûoni . Taurus íst \ únder demo síbenstirne .
Etymology	Gmc */sehwa-/	Gmc */grasa-/	Gmc */kussja-/	Gmc */grasa-/
OHG lexeme	forasehan, 16	gras, 38	kussen, 24	gras, 38
MHG lexeme	voresēhen	gras	küssen	gras
Latin gloss	'praevidere'	'herba'	'osculari'	'herba'
German gloss	'vorhersehen'	'Wiese'	'küssen'	'Wiese'
English gloss	'forsee'	'grass'	'kiss'	'grass'
Class	Verb str (5), past part	Noun str (a)	Verb wk (ja), pres part	Noun str (a)
Inflection	neut acc pl	neut dat sg	masc nom pl	neut nom sg
Citation	Nb24121 : I, 317, 23	Nb08413 : I, 97, 17	Nc11019 : I, 792, 26	Nc06517 : I, 750, 11
Notes	The word for 'see' in Germanic has both a /w/ and /h/ in it, */sehwa-/. In standard English you see one consonant adopted <i>saw</i> , while in German you see the other <i>sah</i> . What was the state in Notker's day?	By now you have read many passages in Carolingian miniscule font, and your eyes are getting comfortable parsing the letters out.	Assume that the English <i>kiss</i> also comes from Germanic */kussja-/. Given German <i>küssen</i> , how could the the Germanic /u/ become /i/ in English?	The next step would be to read the actual manuscripts, what Piper or the Brothers Grimm worked off of, one or two centuries ago. To do that, search for 'Notker Psalms Titus' or 'Notker Boethius Titus', and click on the manuscript photo.

	<u>Word Initial, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Final</u>	<u>Word Final, Syl Final</u>
/Vs/ Morphemic	Not Found	/gɪ+bu <u>es</u> +je+nn+ɪ/	Not Found	/bu <u>es</u> /
Assign stress		[gɪ+b <u>ú</u> es+je+nn+ɪ]		[b <u>ú</u> es]
Syllabification		[gɪ.b <u>ú</u> e.sjen.nɪ]		
Raising				
Rounding				
Words assembled				
Fronting		[gɪ.b <u>ú</u> e.sjen.nɪ]		
V-Reduction		[gɪ.b <u>ú</u> e.sən.nɪ]		
Fortition				
Assimilation				
Epenthesis				
Lenition				
C-Reduction				
Elision				[p <u>ú</u> es]
Lowering				
Speech->Writing		<ge b <u>u</u> ozenne>		<p <u>u</u> oz>
Variation		<ge b <u>ü</u> ezenne>		
Miniscule		Et in\sanabilis . uel difficile mobilis existat affectus . Unde \ imo d <u>iu</u> s <u>o</u> getâna ânachómeni . \ úbel sí ze_g <u>eb</u> üezenne .		únde sí ánderên \ scáncta . dáz ér trínchen neuuóltá . tô t <u>é</u> ta ín is mercurius p <u>ú</u> oz . mít sínero uirga . d <u>iu</u> ca\duceus kenémmet uuás .
Etymology		Gmc */bötja-/		Gmc */bötō/
OHG lexeme		buozen, 55		buoz, 8
MHG lexeme		büezen		buoz
Latin gloss		'paenitere'		'paenitentia'
German gloss		'büßen'		'Buße'
English gloss		'repent'		'repentance'
Class		Verb wk (ja), inf		Noun str (ō)
Inflection		neut dat sg		fem nom sg, uninflected
Citation		Nk09524 : I, 450, 27		Nb20002 : I, 253, 6
Notes		The Titus texts are mostly hand entered, and a delight to read. The current address is: https://titus.uni-frankfurt.de/indexe.htm	Here you click on Old High German, or other languages. And in Notker, you can again see the actual manuscript page photos from Saint Gall.	A more advanced research tool is ANNIS. To view either search 'Notker ANNIS', or try the current address at https://korpling.german.hu-berlin.de/annis3/

	<u>Word Initial, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Final</u>	<u>Word Final, Syl Final</u>
/Vts/ Morphemic	/un+gɪ+tsa:m+j+ižɪ+u:n/	/vro:n+u+žkɑts+iž/	/mižž+j+žats+t+iw/	/vro:n+u+žkɑts/
Assign stress	[ún+gɪ+tsà:m+j+ižɪ+u:n]	[vró:n+u+žkɑts+iž]	[mížž+j+žàts+t+iw]	[vró:n+u+žkɑts]
Syllabification	[ún.gɪ.tsà:.mjǐ.žɪu:n]	[vró:.nʊ.žkɑ.tsɪž]	[míž.žjɪ.žàt.stiw]	[vró:.nʊ.žkɑts]
Raising				
Rounding			[míž.žjɪ.žàt.stü:]	
Words assembled				
Fronting	[ún.gɪ.tsæ:.mjǐ.žɪu:n]			
V-Reduction	[ún.gɪ.tsæ:.mǐ.žɪu:n]	[vró:.nʊ.žkɑ.tsəž]	[míž.šɪ.žàt.stü:]	
Fortition	[ún.gɪ.tsæ:.mǐ.štɪu:n]	[vró:.nʊ.škɑ.tsəž]	[míž.šɪ.žàt.stü:]	[vró:.nʊ.škɑts]
Assimilation	[ún.ɲ.gɪ.tsæ:.mǐ.štɪu:n]			
Epenthesis				
Lenition				
C-Reduction				
Elision				
Lowering				
Speech->Writing	<ún ge zâmestun>	<urôno scázzes>	<misse sáztiu>	<urôno skáz>
Variation		<frôno scázzes>		<frôno scáz>
Miniscule	dāz sī ūber-dēnetiu ne\helle . \ nōh sī fōre slāchi ze ūnlūtrēiste nesī. Dīu hōhesta uuār\ba . ūnde dīu nīderōsta . die sīnt fōre ūn-mēze ūngezâmestūn.	Censores \ uuīelten frôno-scázzes . ter in erario gehānten uuās . fōne dīu \ hīezen sie a censu censores .	uel uerba . idem significant . Misse sáztiu nomi\na alde uerba neuuēhselont nieht ten sin propo\sitium .	ūnde ópferotōn dār tauros . ūnde ūmbe gemēina frōuui . \ nām man frôno-scáz . ūzer demo erario . ūnde gēbeta āl\lemo demo búrglūte
Etymology	Gmc */tēmja-/	Gmc */frauja-/, */skatta-/	Gmc */missa-/, */satja-/	Gmc */frauja-/, */skatta-/
OHG lexeme	ungizāmi, 7	frōnoskaz, 2	missasezzen, 5	frōnoskaz, 2
MHG lexeme	ungezæme	vrôn, schaz	misse, setzen	vrôn, schaz
Latin gloss	'indecorus'	'aerarium'	'transponere'	'aerarium'
German gloss	'unziemlich'	'Staatskasse'	'umstellen'	'Staatskasse'
English gloss	'unseemly'	'treasury'	'change place'	'treasury'
Class	Adj (j)	Noun str (a)	Verb wk (ja), part part	Noun str (a)
Inflection	fem nom pl superl wk	masc gen sg	neut nom pl	masc acc sg
Citattation	Nm01119 : I, 855, 5	Nb12730 : I, 150, 32	Ni19910 : I, 547, 6	Nb06505 : I, 75, 26
Notes	Six morphemes in this one, and you can see the English word <i>tame</i> in one of them. We also draw on Notker's only purely Old Alemannic work here, so with no Latin in it - the shorter text 'De Musica'.	This word and the German word <i>Frau</i> may have echoes back into the Germanic gods.	Your writer's fortition rule only changes the second fricative in /mižž+j/, but leave the first as lenis [míž.šɪ]. Could things have leveled to [míš.šɪ] later? How can we tell?	The word <urôno> in Notker ends in an [n], while the Germanic form */frauja-/ is a form without that ending. Does that [n] have another affect on the word?

	<u>Word Initial, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Final</u>	<u>Word Final, Syl Final</u>
/ld/ Morphemic	/wehž+a _l /+/d _i ng+u/	/gɪ+pfedel/+/gòld+o:+t+ɪ/	/uber+guld+t+ɪmu/	/gold/
Assign stress	[wéhž+ä _l]+[d _i ng+u]	[gɪ+pfedel]+[gòld+o:+t+ɪ]	[úber+gùld+t+ɪmu]	[góld]
Syllabification	[wéh.žä _l]+[d _i n.gu]	[gɪ.pfé.del]+[gòl.do:.tɪ]	[ú.ber.gùld.tɪ.mu]	
Raising				
Rounding				
Words assembled	[wéh.žä _l .d _i n.gu]	[gɪ.pfé.del.gòl.do:.tɪ]		
Fronting				
V-Reduction		[gɪ.pfé.dəl.gòl.du.tɪ]	[ú.bər.gùld.tɪ.mu]	
Fortition	[wéh.šä _l .d _i n.gu]			[kóld]
Assimilation	[wéh.šə _l .d _i n.gu]			
Epenthesis				
Lenition				
C-Reduction				
Elision				
Lowering				
Speech->Writing	<uuéhsal d _i ngo>	<ge fédel góldote>	<úber gúltimo>	<kóld>
Variation		<ge fédel goldôte>	<úber gúltimo>	<cóld>
Miniscule	Állero d _i ngo gebúrt . únde állero uuéhsel- d _i ngo f _{ar} t . únde ál daz síh ín deheínauuís \ uuéget . taz hábet ál fōne dero stätigi des kōtes uuístuomes .	Tû uuândist sélbiz taz sîn fāhs uuésen güldinez . \ únde síne lóccha gefédelgoldôte . Fédelgöld . taz chit f\lo dúnne góld .	ITE IN IGNEM AETERNVM . \ In uestitu deaurato . In übergultimo geuuâte . daz chit mit démo \ uuístuōmis \ gegáreuuē sapientiē .	Tóh ter frécho mán . sámo ríche uuórte\ñêr . sámo so ímo xúo rínne daz cóld . sínen scáz tés \ ímo níomêr fóllún nedúnchet .
Etymology	Gmc */wihsla-/, Gmc */þenga-/	Gmc */gulþa-/	Gmc */gulþja-/	Gmc */gulþa-/
OHG lexeme	wehsalding, 1	gipfedalgoldōn, 1	ubargulden, 2	gold, 80
MHG lexeme	Not Found	Not Found	über + gülden	golt
Latin gloss	'natura mutabilis'	'bratteare'	'deaurare'	'aurum'
German gloss	'veränderliches Wesen'	'mit Blattgold vergolden'	'vergolden'	'Gold'
English gloss	'changeable essence'	'gild with gold leaf'	'gild'	'gold'
Class	Noun neut str (a)	Verb wk (ō), past part	Verb (ja), past part	Noun str (a)
Inflection	neut gen pl	masc acc pl	neut dat sg	neut nom sg
Citotation	Nb21305 : I, 274, 22	Nc07014 : I, 754, 24	Np15615 : II, 171, 14	Nb12304 : I, 144, 28
Notes	Note that your writer has modern German <Wechsel> broken into two morphemes /wehž+a _l /, giving [wéh.šə _l]. What vowel would be in the second element, if he had posited only one morpheme? And would the /h/ be a different phoneme?	The first element is from Vulgar Latin (VLatin) <petalum>, English petal. The /p/ shifted to /pf/, but the /t/ did not shift to /s/, but instead comes across as /d/. Why? The answer may be in sound changes in Latin.	We have a /u/ in the word for 'gold' here, but an /o/ in the words for 'gold' to the right and left column. Why is that? For a hint, look at the Germanic root.	Looking at the left column, Notker writes <lt> when your writer posits two dental stops after the liquid. Is he correct, or should that <lt> just mark one [l.t]. If two [ld.t], what would motivate Notker to just spell <lt>?

	<u>Word Initial, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Final</u>	<u>Word Final, Syl Final</u>
/lt/ Morphemic	/konʒu +/tet+e/	/gi+dri+va t+o:+t+e:r/	Not Found	/werlt+/tsimber/
Assign stress	[kónʒu]+[tét+e]	[gi+drí+vǎ t+o:+t+e:r]		[wér t]+[tsímber]
Syllabification	[kón.ʒu]+[té.te]	[gi.drí.vǎ .to:.te:r]		[wér t]+[tsím.ber]
Raising				
Rounding				
Words assembled	[kón.ʒu .té.te]			[wér t.tsím.ber]
Fronting				
V-Reduction	[kón.ʒəl.té.te]	[gi.drí.vē .tu.te:r]		[wér t.tsím.bər]
Fortition		[ki.drí.vē .tu.te:r]		
Assimilation	[kón.ʒəl.té.te]			
Epenthesis				
Lenition				
C-Reduction				
Elision				
Lowering				
Speech->Writing	<consul_téta>	<ke drífal totêr>		<uuér t zímber>
Variation				
Miniscule	Témo fólgeta \ io magister militum . únde dén uuéleta ér imo sélbo ! also der \ consul téta sînen legatum . Nâh ín uuâren tribuni plebis . ke\uuá rtigôsten .	dâz \ ternarius kedrífal totêr . tûot nouenarium . únde quaternarius keʒu \ua totêr \ . octonarium mácht .		Únde dîz íst tēr nâgel . íoh tíu stíura . mít tērodaz \ uuér t-zímber gehá ten uuírt . stâte . únde úngeuuértet .
Etymology	Gmc */dōn/	Gmc */pri-/, */falda-/		Gmc */wirdaldō-/, */temra-/
OHG lexeme	tuon, 2566	drīfaltōn, 2		weraltzimbar, 3
MHG lexeme	tuon	drīvalten		Not found
Latin gloss	'facere'	'triplicare'		'machina caeli'
German gloss	'tun'	'verdreifachen'		'Kosmos'
English gloss	'do'	'triple'		'universe'
Class	Verb anom	Verb wk (ō), past part		Noun str (a)
Inflection	3rd sg past	masc nom sg		neut nom sg
Citation	Nb12720 : I, 150, 20	Nc09808 : I, 781, 4		Nb17409 : I, 214, 1
Notes	Here a Latin word precedes the Old Alemannic one, and your writer has Notker pronouncing it with a heavy, Old Alemannic accent. How would you change [kón.ʒəl] for <consul> to make it less Alemannic, and maybe more Romance?	The hardest sound here may be the vowel in <i>three</i> . Notker has it short (as <í> instead of <î>), but an OHG dictionary has it long <drī>.	Later on you will see the number <i>two</i> , and notes on English <i>two</i> , <i>twain</i> , <i>twilight</i> , <i>twins</i> , <i>twice</i> . Could <i>three</i> and <i>thrice</i> have had a similar variation?	Again, put yourself in Notker's place, and attempt to gloss 'the universe' for a room full of shivering, adolescent sons of peasants. He relates the universe to a village - with each world a timber built hovel.

	<u>Word Initial, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Final</u>	<u>Word Final, Syl Final</u>
/lž/ Morphemic	/žwegel+/žang+iž/	/halž+i/		/halž/
Assign stress	[žwégel][žáng+iž]	[háłž+i]		[háłž]
Syllabification	[žwé.gel.žán.giž]	[háł.ži]		
Raising				
Rounding				
Words assembled	[žwé.gel.žàn.giž]			
Fronting				
V-Reduction	[žwé.gəl.žàn.gəž]			
Fortition				
Assimilation	[žwé.gəl.žàŋ.gəž]			
Epenthesis				
Lenition				
C-Reduction				
Elision				
Lowering				
Speech->Writing	<suégel_sánges>	<háłse>		<háłs>
Variation				
Miniscule	Dâr negemáŋgta suégelsánges . nóh séitsánges . \ nóh téro fólleglichi dero órgenlútun .	Ultimus labor . i . in ultimo labore . sustulit cęlum inreflexo collo . \ În demo lézesten síge . inthúob er den hímel . mít únuuichentemo háłse .		Dominus iustus concidet \ ceruices peccatorum . Der rehro trubten . hóuuet den iro hals . Confundantur et auertantur retrorsum .
Etymology	Gmc /swiglō-/ , */sangwa-/	Gmc */halsa-/		Gmc */halsa-/
OHG lexeme	swegalsang, 1	hals (1)		hals (1)
MHG lexeme	Not Found	hals		hals
Latin gloss	'melos tibiaryum'	collum		collum
German gloss	'Flötenmelodie'	'Hals'		'Hals'
English gloss	'flute melody'	'throat'		'throat'
Class	Nouns str (a)	Noun str (a)		Noun str (a)
Inflection	neut gen sg	masc dat sg		masc nom sg
Citation	Nc10604 : I, 788, 18	Nb23006 : I, 301, 4		Np49512 : II, 599, 17
Notes	Notker is always thinking of his students, a writer who writes for his reader. Maybe some students came from villages wealthy enough to have flutes, maybe others not. Regardless, there were birds in every village, and all students could relate to their singing.	A word that has come down remarkably unchanged into modern German. But what about the Latin gloss, is it related to the German? What would argue for or against?		How would this be spelled if the fricative were /s/? For a guess, see /rs/ and the word for 'knife'. That's the guess that your writer will make on the next page, when he tries to reconstruct the word for 'mushroom'.

	<u>Word Initial, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Final</u>	<u>Word Final, Syl Final</u>
/ls/ Morphemic	Not Found	Not Found	Not Found	Not Found
Assign stress				
Syllabification				
Raising				
Rounding				
Words assembled				
Fronting				
V-Reduction				
Fortition				
Assimilation				
Epenthesis				
Lenition				
C-Reduction				
Elision				
Lowering				
Speech->Writing				
Variation				
Miniscule				
Etymology				
OHG lexeme				
MHG lexeme				
Latin gloss				
German gloss				
English gloss				
Class				
Inflection				
Citation				
Notes		<p>One example here might be <uu<u>il</u>ze>, which names a tribe glossed in Latin as <Ve<u>le</u>tabus>. Though as a (ja) stem, its /t/ may have been geminated to /tt/ before /j/, and so shifted to /ts/ in [w<u>il</u>.<u>ts</u>ɪ].</p>		<p>Although Koebler finds 15 examples of <bu<u>li</u>z> (Modern German <i>P<u>il</u>z</i> [p<u>il</u>s] 'mushroom') in OHG texts, the word does not occur in Notker. It is borrowed from Vulgar Latin <bo<u>le</u>tus>, and occurs as <bu<u>l</u>z> [b<u>u</u>l̩s] in MHG.</p>

	<u>Word Initial, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Final</u>	<u>Word Final, Syl Final</u>
/lts/ Morphemic	/luts+il/+/tsorn+ag/	/halts+u/	/gɪ+žmalts+t+ɪs/	/halts/
Assign stress	[lúts+ĭl]+[tsórn+äg]	[háłts+u]	[gɪ+žmáłts+t+ɪs]	[háłts]
Syllabification	[lú.tsĭl]+[tsór.näg]	[háł.tsu]	[gɪ.žmáłt.stɪs]	
Raising				
Rounding				
Words assembled	[lú.tsĭl.tsór.näg]			
Fronting	[lú.tsĭl.tsór.näg]			
V-Reduction	[lú.tsɪł.tsór.nɛg]		[gɪ.žmáłt.stəs]	
Fortition				
Assimilation				
Epenthesis				
Lenition				
C-Reduction				
Elision				
Lowering				
Speech->Writing	<lúzzel_zórneg>	<háłzo>	<ge smáłztez>	<háłz>
Variation				
Miniscule	Únde mīr trāne rēcchende . mīt \ ıro uuórten . Commota paulisper . Sār dēs ěin lúzzel_zórneg_uuór\tenıú . \ Ac toruis inflammata luminibus .	Chām óuh ěin háłz smíd . Uuánda fiur hábet ıo úngréh\ten gāngħ . únde ıx prıchet ıo ze_ěin-uuéderro hēnde . sámosô \ der háłzo .	In diēn uuórten** gāb iū moyses israhelitis \ ze_trınchenne caput (daz hou̅bet) uituli (chalbis) . ze ērest in_fıure gesmáłztez .	Quidam etiam claudus faber \ uenit . Chām óuh ěin háłz smíd . Uuánda fiur hábet ıo úngréh\ten \ gāngħ .
Etymology	Gmc */lutta-/, */turna-/	Gmc */halta-/	Gmc */smaltja-/	Gmc */halta-/
OHG lexeme	zornag, 17	halz, 25	smelzen, 10	halz, 25
MHG lexeme	zornec	halz	smelzen	halz
Latin gloss	'commutus'	'claudus'	'liquare'	'claudus'
German gloss	'erzürnt'	'lahm'	'auflösen'	'lahm'
English gloss	'incensed'	'lame'	'dissolve'	'lame'
Class	Adv	Adj	Verb wk (ja), past part	Adj
Inflection	uninflected	masc nom sg wk	neut acc sg	uninflected
Citation	Nb00920 : I, 11, 20	Nc07616 : I, 760, 24	Np26314 : II, 296, 24	Nc07614 : I, 760, 23
Notes	Notker's language draws on Germanic words that still exist in English, but are no longer used in Modern German. You likely see <i>little</i> above. If so, what two steps do we need to posit, to derive the English vowel from Germanic */lutta-/?	And others survive into English, but are more arcane, as the English word <i>halt</i> is for 'lame'.	Is there a relationship between English 'melt' and German 'schmelzen'? If so, what a weird sound change. Or maybe not so weird, for a toddler playing with words?	In Modern German, adjectives are inflected when modifying a noun, but uninflected in the predicate of a sentence (ex: <i>Der nette Hund ist nett</i>). In Notker's day, the grammatical rules seem less codified, as with <Chām óuh ěin háłz smíd>.

	<u>Word Initial, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Final</u>	<u>Word Final, Syl Final</u>
/rd/ Morphemic	/vɪr.dien+o:+NTT+IN/	/mann+/werd+e+nn/+i:/	Not Found	/un+werd/
Assign stress	[vɪr.díeŋ+o:+NTT+IN]	[mánŋ]+[wérd+e+nn/+i:]		[ún+wèrd]
Syllabification	[vɪr.díe.no:NT.TIN]	[mánŋ]+[wèr.denn]+i:]		[ún.wèrd]
Raising				
Rounding				
Words assembled		[mánŋ.wèr.denn]+[i:]		
Fronting				
V-Reduction	[vər.díe.nəNT.tən]	[mánŋ.wèr.dənn]+[i:]		
Fortition	[fər.díe.nəNT.tən]			
Assimilation	[fər.díe.nəNT.tən]			
Epenthesis				
Lenition				
C-Reduction		[mán.wèr.dən]+[i:]		
Elision				
Lowering				
Speech->Writing	<fer_dienonten>	<mán uuérden î>		<ún uuérd>
Variation		<man uuérdini>		
Miniscule	Nû ládont ín ze hūon sélben die zīte . uuóla dāz ferdienonten mīt lobesamen árbeiten . únde sīn \ sélbes chréftīg éllen . héizet ín nū ána-gehūien .	Alde irgízet er ze \ man-uuérdini \ sceīnenne dīa gnāda sinero incarnationis . die er geheízzen há\bet?		Catullus uuás ueronensis poe\ta . nobilis . pedíu uuás ímo nonius únuuérđ . tér fō\ne gallia ze_roma chómenêr . mīt gothorum suffragio
Etymology	Gmc */pewanō/	Gmc */werpa-/		Gmc */unwerpa-/
OHG lexeme	firdionōn, 2	manwerdanī, 1		unwerđ, 17
MHG lexeme	verdienen	man, wërden		unwërt
Latin gloss	'merere'	'incarnatio'		'contemptibilis'
German gloss	'verdienen'	'Menschwerdung'		'verächtlich'
English gloss	'earn'	'incarnation'		'contemptible'
Class	Verb wk (ō), pres part.	Noun str (ī).		Adj.
Inflection	masc acc sg	fem gen sg		uninflected
Citation	Nc08216 : I, 766, 5	Np27315 : II, 308, 25		Nb12329 : I, 145, 27
Notes	All three of these examples show a thorn in Germanic, written /p/ usually, although sometimes the Greek symbol theta /θ/ is used. It's always the voiceless (fortis) 'th' in 'think', not the voiced (lenis) in 'these'.	The only way that your writer can reconstruct this form is to skip assembling the word, and leave it as two words. It is as if Notker said two words - 'being' plus 'ism'.	How would <uuérdeni> be spelled, if this word for 'incarnation' were a common concept in Old Alemannic, and the morphemically /werd+e+nn+i:/?	Note the spelling in MHG, where Germanic /e/ gets written with an umlaut over it, as <unwërt> from Germanic */unwerpa-/. Yet it's not umlauted at all, but the original Germanic /e/. How confusing is that?

	<u>Word Initial, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Final</u>	<u>Word Final, Syl Final</u>
/rt/ Morphemic	/vɪr+tɪ:lɪg+o:+t+o:ʒɾ/	/un+gɪ+wɑrt+je+t/	/un+gɪ+wɑrt+t+o:ʒɾ+e/	/u:s+wɛrt/
Assign stress	[vɪr+tɪ:lɪg+o:+t+o:ʒɾ]	[ún+gɪ+wàrt+je+t]	[ún+gɪ+wàrt+t+ö:ʒɾ+e]	[ú:s+wért]
Syllabification	[vɪr.tɪ:lɪ.go:.to:ʒɾ]	[ún.gɪ.wàr.tjet]	[ún.gɪ.wàrt.tö:.ʒɾe]	[ú:s.wért]
Raising		[ún.gɪ.wär.tjet]		
Rounding				
Words assembled				
Fronting				
V-Reduction	[vər.tɪ:lɪ.gu.to:ʒɾ]	[ún.gɪ.wär.tət]	[ún.gɪ.wàrt.tʊ.ʒɾe]	
Fortition	[vər.tɪ:lɪ.gu.to:ʃt]		[ún.gɪ.wàrt.tʊ.ʃte]	
Assimilation		[ún.gɪ.wär.tət]	[ún.gɪ.wàrt.tʊ.ʃte]	
Epenthesis				
Lenition				
C-Reduction				
Elision				
Lowering				
Speech->Writing	<uer_tîlegotôst>	<ún ge uuértet>	<ún ge uuártosta>	<ûz uuért>
Variation	<uer_tîlegotost>		<ún ge uuártôsta>	
Miniscule	Trûhten dû uer t îlegotost íro bîlde in dînero burg . uuanda siê niêht ne-chô\ment \ ze hîmele . dâr siê dih kesêhen .	Únde dîz íst têr nâgel . íoh tíu stîura . mít têrodaz \ uuêrlt-zîmber gehâltten uuírt . stâte . únde ungeuuártet .	Hárto gérho uuólti er \ sophiam . dâz chîr sapientiam . uuânda sí uuízzig únde héilig \ íst . únde ungeuuártôsta íst . íoh skônista íst .	Quamuis afficiant instrumenta sensuum . forinsecus biectęqualitates . \ Tóh tíu ûz u é r t pegágenenten bîlde ána uuérdên . diu óugen .
Etymology	Gmc */diligō-/	Gmc */wardj-/	*Gmc /wardj-/	Gmc */ūt/, */werda-/
OHG lexeme	firtiligōn, 47	werten, 3	werten, 3	ūzwert, 11
MHG lexeme	vertiligen	werten	werten	ūzwért
Latin gloss	'extinguere'	'incorruptus facere '	'incorruptus facere '	'forinsecus'
German gloss	'auslöschen'	'unvergänglich machen'	'unvergänglich machen'	'außen'
English gloss	'extinguish'	'make imperishable'	'make imperishable'	'outside'
Class	Verb wk (ō).	Verb wk (ja), past part.	Verb wk (ja), past part.	Adv.
Inflection	2nd sg past	uninflected	fem nom sg superl wk	uninflected
Citation	Np25810 : II, 291, 3	Nb17409 : I, 214, 1	Nc01101 : I, 696, 11	Nx25820 : I, 342, 19
Notes	We have had several examples now of a long unstressed (or tertiary stressed) vowel, and how it remains if the last syllable of a word, but shortens if it followed by another syllable. So <uertilegotôst>, not *<uertilegôtôst>.	Compare this weak (ja) form */wardj-/ for Old Alemannic /rt/ against the previous page where you saw */werpa-/.	By now you should be able to say which form of of the strong verb (Modern German <i>werden</i>) was used in the weak (ja) form, and how that changed the word's meaning.	The pattern <wVrT> (where V=any vowel, and T=any dental) is one of the hardest patterns to parse out in Notker, as you see roots for 'worth/value', 'ward/guard' and 'worth/become'. Did your writer get this one right?

	<u>Word Initial, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Final</u>	<u>Word Final, Syl Final</u>
/rž/ Morphemic	/er/+/žúnn+e/+/wánt+i:g+e:r/	/verž+in/	Not Found	/reb+e+mas+i+rž/
Assign stress	[ér]+[žúnn+e]+[wánt+i:g+e:r]	[vérž+in]		[réb+e+màs+i+rž]
Syllabification	[ér].[žún.ne]+[wán.τī:.ge:r]	[vér.žin]		[ré.be.mà.sirž]
Raising	[ér].[žún.ne]+[wän.τī:.ge:r]			[ré.be.mä.sirž]
Rounding				
Words assembled	[ér.žún.ne.wän.τī:.ge:r]			
Fronting				
V-Reduction	[ér.žún.ne.wän.τī.ge:r]	[vér.žən]		[ré.be.mä.sirž]
Fortition				
Assimilation	[ér.žún.ne.wän.τī.ge:r]			
Epenthesis				
Lenition	[ér.žún.ne.wän.dī.ge:r]			
C-Reduction				
Elision				
Lowering				
Speech->Writing	<ér_súnna uuéndigêr>	<uérſen>		<réba-mézers>
Variation	<ér_súnna uuéndiger>			<rebemezers>
Miniscule	Pe_díu hábet er dén námén . \ dáz er_súnna-uuéndiger héizet . Dér íst uirgini únde septembrio gegé\ben . uuánda díu grûoni ín_démo mânode begínnēt kân in rôti .	His uersibus conquesta est . de perturbatione nostrę mentis . Chlá\geta si síh mít tisen uérſen . mînes únmuotes .		Falcemque dextera . leua gestans cratera somni\ficum . \ Sín rebemezers án dero zéseuuun trágende .
Etymology	Gmc */sunnō-/ , */wandja-/	ELat <versum>		Gmc */rebō-/ , */matisahsa-/
OHG lexeme	sunnawentig, 1	fers, 22		rebamezziras, 5
MHG lexeme	sunne, wendic	vërs		mezzar
Latin gloss	'heliotropius'	'versus'		'falx'
German gloss	'sonnenwendend'	'Vers'		'Rebmesser'
English gloss	heliotropic'	'verse'		'pruning knife'
Class	Adj	Noun str (a)		Noun str (a)
Inflection	masc nom sg	masc dat pl		neut acc sg
Citation	Nb06803 : I, 752, 17	Nb01108 : I, 13, 17		Nc02322 : I, 758, 4
Notes	A heliotropic flower is one that turns towards the sun during the day, as it tries to stay facing the sun. In English, the most famous of these is the sunflower, or at least when it is young.	Your writer sources this word to ELatin, but the word for 'verse' must have existed long before Notker's day, when VLatin words were borrowed in. Maybe some words get borrowed in multiple times over the centuries?	From the Latin Latin Vulgate Bible, words could be borrowed in again and again for over 1,000 years. Is that why German <i>predigen</i> (CLatin <i>predicare</i> , English <i>preach</i>) does not have a shifted <pf>?	So German 'Messer' may really be from two words, first */sahsa-/ or short sword, as in the Saxons. But what is */mati-/ refer to? What was this sword used to cut? And how did such a proud weapon diminish further into something to prune grape vines?

	<u>Word Initial, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Final</u>	<u>Word Final, Syl Final</u>
/rs/ Morphemic	Not Found	/h <u>ir</u> s+ <u>iž</u> /	Not Found	/h <u>ir</u> s/
Assign stress		[h <u>ir</u> s+ <u>iž</u>]		[h <u>ir</u> s]
Syllabification		[h <u>ir</u> . <u>s</u> iž]		
Raising				
Rounding				
Words assembled				
Fronting				
V-Reduction		[h <u>ir</u> . <u>səž</u>]		
Fortition				
Assimilation				
Epenthesis				
Lenition				
C-Reduction				
Elision				
Lowering				
Speech->Writing		<h <u>ir</u> zes>		<h <u>ir</u> z>
Variation				
Miniscule		Qui perfecit pedes meos . tamquam cerui . Der mîne fuôze ge\lân hâbet snêlle sâmo so h <u>ir</u> zes . ze úber scrícchene des tiêueles \ stríccha .		Hirco\ceruus enim significat aliquid . Hircoceruus \ pezeíchenet . táz péidiu sâment íst . póg iób \ h <u>ir</u> z . únde íst compositum nomen .
Etymology		Gmc */hiruta-/ hiruz, 30		Gmc */hiruta-/ hiruz, 30
OHG lexeme		hirz		hirz
MHG lexeme		'cervus'		'cervus'
Latin gloss		'Hirsch'		'Hirsch'
German gloss		'deer'		'deer'
English gloss		Noun str (a)		Noun str (a)
Class		masc gen sg		masc nom sg
Inflection		Np05311, II, 53, 25		Ni14701 : I, 502, 5
Citattation				
Notes		Standard German <i>Hir<u>sch</u></i> is pronounced with a palatized /š/, but that is perhaps a later and unrelated development, influenced by the preceding liquid.		Why would Notker draw on a spelling rule, so that the words for both <i>Her<u>z</u></i> and <i>Hir<u>sch</u></i> ended in the same <z>? What could motivate him to spell both [rts] and [rs] with the same <rz> letters word finally?

	<u>Word Initial, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Final</u>	<u>Word Final, Syl Final</u>
/rts/ Morphemic	/waser+/tsežž+u/	/harts+/ag+imv/	/žwarts+t+e:r/	/harts/
Assign stress	[wáser]+[tsèžž+u]	[hárts+äg+imv]	/žwárts+t+e:r/	[hárts]
Syllabification	[wá.ser]+[tsèž.žv]	[hár.tsä.gɪ.mu]	[žwárts.te:r]	
Raising				
Rounding				
Words assembled	[wá.ser.tsèž.žv]			
Fronting				
V-Reduction	[wá.sər.tsèž.žv]	[hár.tsě.gɪ.mu]		
Fortition	[wá.sər.tsèž.šv]	[hár.tsě.gɪ.mu]		
Assimilation				
Epenthesis				
Lenition				
C-Reduction				
Elision				
Lowering				
Speech->Writing	<uuázer_zéss>	<hárzegemo>	<suárztêr>	<hárz>
Variation		<hárzegemo>		
Miniscule	únde fōne de\ro níderun náxi . nelâzet tie hína-fārenten animas mīt ke\máche hína- fāren . sie dār io-ána dúnchonde sámó-so in_éine\ro uuázer-zéssó .	uuárf \ sí sie in_dia blūot-fāreuuun zéssa martis . álde gáb sie dero \ blāuuun áhō saturni . ze_fersklíndenne in hárzegemo slúche .	Similiter dispositus ad nigredinem . \ affectus nigredine . suárzentêr . éteuuáz \ suárzêr . sámó suárztêr .	álsó flíed únde hárz . \ únde diu ába dien bóumen in dáz uuázer fállendo ze_stéine er\hártet .
Etymology	Gmc */watar/	*/harta-/	*/swartja-/	*/harta-/
OHG lexeme	wazzarzessa, 2	harzag, 1	swerzen, 2	harz, 34
MHG lexeme	wazzer, zesse	harzec	swerzen	harz
Latin gloss	'tempestas aquae'	'piceus'	fuscare	'pix'
German gloss	'Wasserflut'	'pechschwarz'	'verdunkeln'	'Pech'
English gloss	'flood of water'	'pitch black'	'darken'	'pitch'
Class	Noun: str (ō)	Adj	Verb wk (ja), past part	Noun str (a)
Inflection	fem dat sg	masc dat sg	masc nom sg	neut nom sg
Citattation	Nc14308 : I, 824, 1	Nc013026 : I, 710, 7	Nk02567 : I, 425, 4	Nc06814 : I, 753, 1
Notes	By now you should be able to relate English <i>water</i> and <i>wet</i> . But what about <i>winter</i> ? Think about the season, if you were huddled on the damp, dirt floor of a hut. Sometimes an /n/ seems to have gotten infixated into words, giving us both <i>st<u>and</u></i> and <i>st<u>ead</u></i> .	To get German <i>Pech</i> and English <i>pitch</i> , what had to happen to the Latin <p> and <c> in <piceus>? What does this tell you about when the word was borrowed into Germanic languages?	If <suárztêr> is an inflected past participle, what vowel would be in an uninflected past participle <suVrztet>?	Linking entries on this page with <i>winter</i> and <i>water</i> and <i>pitch</i> , what would Notker's <hárz> have been used for? Think of water-proofing a boat or well bucket, or even those valuable wine casks, with pine tar or other tree resin. A Greek wine, Retsina, is still flavored with pine

	<u>Word Initial, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Final</u>	<u>Word Final, Syl Final</u>
/nd/ Morphemic	/lob+I+žam/+/dun(k)x+je+t/	/munT+Iž/	/manT+/t+o:n/	/munT/
Assign stress	[lób+I+žám]+[dún(k)x+je+t]	[múnT+Iž]	[máT]+[t+o:n]	[múnT]
Syllabification	[ló.bI.žám]+[dún(k).xjet]	[mún.TIž]	[máT]+[to:n]	
Raising				
Rounding				
Words assembled	[ló.bI.žám.dún(k).xjet]		[máT.to:n]	
Fronting	[ló.bI.žám]+[dún(k).xjet]			
V-Reduction	[ló.bI.žám.dún(k).xət]	[mún.Təž]		
Fortition				
Assimilation	[ló.bI.žàn.dún(k).xət]	[mún.təž]	[máT.to:n]	[múnT]
Epenthesis	[ló.bI.žàn.dúnk.xət]			
Lenition		[mún.dəž]		
C-Reduction	[ló.bI.žàn.dúnk.xət]			
Elision				
Lowering				
Speech->Writing	<lóbesám dunchet>	<múndes>	<mántôn>	<múnt>
Variation	<lóbesám dunchet>		<mánton>	
Miniscule	Ne\mág íuuih óuh táx írren na? Ut quod apud alios laude . apud alios suppli\cio dignum iudicetur? Sô hártto . dáx éinên lóbesám dunchet .	Sô philosophia léno úndemánmen\do súš kesāng . mít zímigi des ánalútttes . únde mít zúhtigi des múndes .	Micheles \ úbeles zígen siê mih . so míne líde die noh in érdo sint mísseta\ten . \ unde mánton íro scúldo . diê ín uuégen solton .	Ταχ hónang íst óuh \ téš-te súoxera . úbe der múnt pe-fóre íeht píttteres ke\chórota .
Etymology	Gmc */þunkja-/	Gmc */munþa-/	Gmc */manþja-/	Gmc */munþa-/
OHG lexeme	dunken, 132	mund, 175	menden, 57	mund, 175
MHG lexeme	dünken	mund	menden	mund
Latin gloss	'videri'	'os'	'gaudere'	'os'
German gloss	'dünken'	'Mund'	'sich freuen'	'Mund'
English gloss	'seem'	'mouth'	'rejoice'	'mouth'
Class	Verb wk (ja)	Noun str (a)	Verb wk (ja)	Noun str (a)
Inflection	3rd sg pres	masc gen sg	3rd pl past	masc nom sg
Citation	Nb09904 : I, 114, 11	Nb18304 : I, 226, 26	Np12908 : II, 139, 21	Np11022 : I, 128, 7
Notes	Here we have another of those ja-verbs, with the usual fronting and also the usual shifting of a Germanic stop */k/ now an affricate (here */k/ to /kx/). Although this isn't a great example, as epenthesis would give us an affricate anyway after a nasal.	Here, without that */j/ afterwards, Germanic */nþ/ becomes just regular [n.d] in Old Alemannic.	But when the */nþ/ is followed by a */j/, we see /nT.t/. That is not an affricate, but a geminate dental stop.	Does that give you a clue on how affricates may have developed from a /p,t,k/ plus /j/, on maybe a middle state?

	<u>Word Initial, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Final</u>	<u>Word Final, Syl Final</u>
/nt/ Morphemic	/fóntt+im/+/trín(k)x+e+nn/	/vriwnt+in/	/bi+wánt/+/t+e/	/vriwnt/
Assign stress	[fóntt+im]+[trín(k)x+e+nn]	[vríwnt+in]	[bi+wánt]+[t+e]	[vríwnt]
Syllabification	[fónt.tim]+[trín(k).xənn]	[vríwn.tin]	[bi.wánt]+[te]	
Raising				
Rounding		[vrü:n.tin]		[vrü:nt]
Words assembled	[fónt.tim.trín(k).xənn]		[bi.wánt.te]	
Fronting				
V-Reduction	[fónt.təm.trín(k).xənn]	[vrü:n.tən]		
Fortition	[fónt.təm.trín(k).xənn]	[vrü:n.tən]	[pɪ.wánt.te]	
Assimilation	[fónt.tən.trín(k).xənn]	[vrü:n.tən]	[pɪ.wánt.te]	[vrü:nt]
Epenthesis	[fónt.tən.trínk.xənn]			
Lenition	[fónt.tən.drínk.xənn]	[vrü:n.dən]		
C-Reduction	[fónt.tən.drínk.xən]			
Elision				
Lowering				
Speech->Writing	<fontem_drínchen>	<uríunden>	<pe uuánta>	<uríunt>
Variation	<fontem_drinchen>			<fríunt>
Miniscule	uuârin mir mîne \ trâne brôt tages unde nâhtes . Die az ih . unde dia fuôra \ gab ih mînero sêlo . do ih fontem_drinchen ne-muôsa .	Úbe dir iz nieht állez kelicho nemisselichêt . táz tír \ in_lôz keuállen íst . úbe du díh tóh ze_dien uríunden uersíst .	CVM CONVERTIT DOMINVS CAPTIVITATEM SYON . \ Dô Got peuuánta daz éllende syon . do uurdén \ uuir samo so getrôstet .	Quid totiens \ iactastis me felicem amici? Uuáz hîezent ir io mih sâligen fríunt mî\ne? Uuâr íst iz nú?
Etymology	Gmc */drenka-/	Gmc */frijōnd-/	Gmc */wandja-/	Gmc */frijōnd-/
OHG lexeme	trinkan, 137	friunt, 86	biwenten, 19	friunt, 86
MHG lexeme	trinken	vriunt	wenden	vriunt
Latin gloss	'bibere'	'amicus'	'convertere'	'amicus'
German gloss	'trinken'	'Freund'	'verwandeln'	'Freund'
English gloss	'drink'	'friend'	'convert'	'friend'
Class	Verb str (3), inf	Noun str (nt)	Verb wk (ja)	Noun str (nt)
Inflection	uninflected	masc dat pl	3rd sg pres	masc nom pl
Citation	Np14124 : II, 154, 7	Nb07018 : I, 81, 20	Np49109 : II, 555, 23	Np00715 : I, 8, 22
Notes	Again a ELatin word followed by an Old Alemannic one. Your writer believes that Notker pronounced both languages the same (even nasal assimilation and lenition in [fónt.tən.drínk.xən].	Think of German <i>Freund</i> and English <i>friend</i> , and then <i>Feind</i> and <i>fiend</i> . Are they linked or not linked? If not linked in meaning, are they linked in structure?	Try reconstructing <fontem> to the far left without Old Alemannic sound rules in the Latin. What happens to the <d> in <drínchen>, from Old Alemannic /trín(k)x+e+nn/?	The word for 'friend' is another of those rare declensions, maybe off of an original verb's present participle (so like English <i>-ing</i> in <i>running</i> , German <i>-end</i> in <i>Lachend</i>).

	<u>Word Initial, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Final</u>	<u>Word Final, Syl Final</u>
/NŽ/ Morphemic	/magen+/žù:l/	/tsue+/gɪ+dunž+n+u:n/	Not Found	/danž/
Assign stress		[tsúe.]+[gɪ+dúnž+n+u:n]		[dánž]
Syllabification	[má.gen].[žù:l]	[tsúe.]+[gɪ.dún.žnu:n]		
Raising				
Rounding				
Words assembled	[má.gen.žù:l]	[tsúe.gɪ.dún.žnu:n]		
Fronting				
V-Reduction	[má.gən.žù:l]			
Fortition				
Assimilation		[tsúe.gɪ.dún.žnu:n]		[dánž]
Epenthesis				
Lenition				
C-Reduction				
Elision				
Lowering				
Speech->Writing	<mágen_sûl>	<zûo ge dúnsenûn>		<dáns>
Variation				
Miniscule	dáz chit zierdâ . únde bechénnedâ dero mágen-chréfte . Also uuír ín demo hûs héixên mágen=sûl . dia méistûn sûl .	Dannan ist diser psalmus asaph . daz chit synago\ge (dero zuô ge\dúnseun) . \ dero uox (stimma) hiêr liútet .		claua \ cerberum traxit triplici catena . Únde geuuâfendêr mít chnúttele . dáns \ er cerberum fône héllô . mít trílero chéténno .
Etymology	Gmc */magana-/, */sûli-/	Gmc */þensa-/		Gmc */þensa-/
OHG lexeme	magansûl, 1	zuodinsan, 1		dinsan, 9
MHG lexeme	main, sûl	dinsen		dinsen
Latin gloss	'columna magna'	'simul trahere'		'simul trahere'
German gloss	'Hauptsäule'	'zusammenziehen'		'zusammenziehen'
English gloss	'main column'	'pull together'		'pull'
Class	Noun str (i)	Verb str (3), past part		Verb str (3)
Inflection	fem acc sg	fem gen sg wk		3rd sg past
Citation	Nb12708 : I, 150, 7	Np25503 : II, 287, 12		Np22909 : I, 299, 30
Notes	Your writer posits four levels of stress in Notker. In the first two, all vowels can contrast, short and long. The first element of a compound (or a stressed, separable prefix followed by root) gets primary stress, the second element gets secondary.	You see both examples here and to the left - one a compound [má.gen.žù:l] and then a stressed prefix [tsúe.gɪ.dún.žnu:n]. This relates to modern German stress in <i>Wóhnhzìmm̄er</i> and <i>vórkòmm̄en</i> .	The acute diacritic <á> marks primary stress, while the grave <à> marks secondary. Tertiary is marked with the breve <ä>. Quaternary (unstressed) is left without diacritic, so just <a>.	Suffixes are given tertiary accent [háj.lī:g] <héilīg> 'holy, nom sg'. Unstressed prefixes, plus inflectional endings, are given quaternary accent [háj.lī.gɪ.mū] <héiligemo> 'holy, dat sg'. Both are reduced environments, where less vowels contrast.

	<u>Word Initial, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Final</u>	<u>Word Final, Syl Final</u>
/ns/ Morphemic	Not Found	/glán(t)s+iw/	/glán(t)s+/te/	/glán(t)s/
Assign stress		[glán(t)s+iw]	[glán(t)s]+[te]	[glán(t)s]
Syllabification		[glán.(t)siw]		
Raising				
Rounding		[glán.(t)sü:]		
Words assembled			[glán(t).ste]	
Fronting				
V-Reduction				
Fortition			[klán(t).ste]	
Assimilation		[glán.(t)sü:]	[klán(t).ste]	[glán(t)s]
Epenthesis		[glán.tsü:]	[klánt.ste]	[glánt्स]
Lenition				
C-Reduction		[glán.tsü:]		
Elision				
Lowering				
Speech->Writing		<glánziu>	<klánzta>	<glánz>
Variation			<clánzta>	
Miniscule		nubes transierunt . Diû selben uuólchen fuôren fône iudea (iudon) ad (ze) gentes (diêten .) . \ sinen oûgon glánziu . doh siû úns sîn tîmberriû .	Tára-nâh légeta si úfen íro hóubet mágedlichen gold\ring . tér méist clánzta fône déro scôni . dero míttun gímmo .	Íh méino uuío íoh sélbes iouis stella . tíu \ fôre filo glánz íst . tanne úrouge uuirt . só diu súnna stât skînen .
Etymology		Gmc */glanta-/	Gmc */glantja-/	Gmc */glanta-/
OHG lexeme		glanz, 4	glenzen, 3	glanz, 4
MHG lexeme		glanz	glenzen	glanz
Latin gloss		lucens'	'lucere'	'lucens'
German gloss		glänzend'	'glänzen'	'glänzend'
English gloss		'shining'	'shine on'	'shining'
Class		Adj	Verb wk (ja)	Adj
Inflection		neut nom pl	3rd sg past	fem nom sg, uninflected
Citation		Np05001 : II, 49, 23	Nc12345 : I, 786, 6	Nc06317 : I, 748, 13
Notes	In the two reduced environments, tertiary and quaternary, Notker drops to three vowels in open syllables - /ɪ, e, u/. He also reduces to these in the second element of diphthongs or long vowels, marked as the non-syllabic off-glides of /j, e, w/.	Your writer writes /i:/ with the length marker for clarity, but he means /ij/. Similarly, /u:/ marks /uw/, while /e:, a:, o:/ all really mark /ee, ae, oe/.	You can see this three-part off-glide in /ij, ie, iw/, [i:, ie, ü:], <î, îe, íu>; /uj, ue, uw/, [ü:, ue, u:], <íu, úo, ú>; /aj, ae, aw/, [äj, a:, ow], <éi, â, óu>.	In quaternary stress, short vowels reduce to just one, the schwa [ə] in closed syllables, while remain three-part in open syllables [ɪ, e, u]. The first element of long vowels (and diphthongs) fully contrast in quaternary and tertiary.

	<u>Word Initial, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Final</u>	<u>Word Final, Syl Final</u>
/nts/ Morphemic	/niwn+tsehen/	Not Found	Not Found	Not Found
Assign stress	[níwn+tsèhen]			
Syllabification	[níwn.tsè.hen]			
Raising				
Rounding	[nú:n.tsè.hen]			
Words assembled				
Fronting				
V-Reduction	[nú:n.tsè.hən]			
Fortition				
Assimilation				
Epenthesis				
Lenition				
C-Reduction				
Elision	[nú:n.tsè:n]			
Lowering				
Speech->Writing	<níun_zên>			
Variation	<níunzen>			
Miniscule	Úbe níunzen slóz \ apodicticę . únde síbiniu dialecticę . uuóla \ gelírnet sín . sô uuízi[n] man dâr-míte .			
Etymology	Gmc */newun/, */tehun/			
OHG lexeme	niunzehan, 4			
MHG lexeme	niunzēhen			
Latin gloss	'undeviginti'			
German gloss	'neunzehn'			
English gloss	'nineteen'			
Class	Number Ordinal			
Inflection	uninflected			
Citation	Ns04705 : I, 619, 25			

Notes

However long vowels (and diphthongs) in tertiary or quaternary stress reduce to single vowels, and also to just that three-part contrast, if not word final. So [hǣj.lī:g] <héilīg> 'holy, nom sg', but [hǣj.lī.gr.mʊ] <héiligemo> 'holy, dat sg'.

To the left we have Notker's words for *nine* and *ten* (which is what the word *nineteen* means, if you think about it for a bit).

In German, these words are *neun* and *zehn*, and in Latin *novem* and *decem*.

Assuming that the Latin forms are nearer the original Indo-European, what changes would you need to list out to get to the English and German forms?

	<u>Word Initial, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Final</u>	<u>Word Final, Syl Final</u>
/Vg/ Morphemic	/nužž+īd+e/+/gɪ+no:t+mes+o:+t/	/gɪ+nueg+j+iw/	/gɪ+nueg/+/t+e/	/gɪ+nueg/
Assign stress	[núžž+īd+e]+[gɪ+nó:t+mès+o:+t]	[gɪ+núeg+j+iw]	[gɪ+núeg]+[t+e]	[gɪ+núeg]
Syllabification	[núž.žī.de]+[gɪ.nó:t.mè.so:t]	[gɪ.núe.gjiw]	[gɪ.núeg]+[te]	[gɪ.núeg]
Raising				
Rounding		[gɪ.núe.gjü:]		
Words assembled	[núž.žī.de.gɪ.nó:t.mè.so:t]		[gɪ.núeg.te]	
Fronting	[núž.žī.de.gɪ.nó:t.mè.so:t]	[gɪ.núe.gjü:]		
V-Reduction	[núž.žīr.de.gnó:t.mè.so:t]	[gnúe.gü:]	[gnúeg.te]	[gnúeg]
Fortition	[núž.šīr.de.gnó:t.mè.so:t]	[knúe.gü:]	[knúeg.te]	[knúeg]
Assimilation				
Epenthesis				
Lenition				
C-Reduction				
Elision				
Lowering				
Speech->Writing	<nísseda gnôt mézôt>	<knúoge>	<knúogta>	<knúog>
Variation		<cnúegíu>	<cnúocta>	
Miniscule	álde gnôt-mezúnga . uuánda diu lex táx uuórt \ spríchet . táx in únguúshéite . únde in_sríte uuésen mág . \ únz sîn bezéichen-nísseda_gnôt-mézôt uuírdet .	Sunt enim naues . quarum remi non sunt . Skéf sínt cnúegíu . \ áne rúoder . tíu man dríbet mít scáltôn	Úzer dien nám hértón apollo . sô filo is cnúoc\ta ze_dien benéimden . diu er túon uuólta .	sô zálo mít \ mír . únde chóro míh úberuuínden . dú neéigíst nóh \ knúog_mánigero sáldôn . Táx tú sálda héizest .
Etymology	*/naud-/, */metō-/	*/ganōgja-/	*/ganōgja-/	*/ganōga-/
OHG lexeme	ginōtmezzōn, 7	ginuogi, 115	ginuogen, 18	ginuog, 44
MHG lexeme	nôt, mezzen	genüec	genüegen	genuoc
Latin gloss	'definire'	'sufficiens'	'sufficere'	'sufficiens'
German gloss	'bestimmen'	'genügend'	'genügen'	'genügend'
English gloss	'define'	'sufficient'	'suffice'	'sufficient'
Class	Verb wk (ō), past part	Adj (ja)	Verb wk (ja)	Adv
Inflection	uninflected	neut nom pl	3rd sg past	undeclined
Citation	Nb05703 : I, 67, 19	Nk07214 : I, 429, 10	Nc02908 : I, 712, 19	Nb06806 : I, 79, 6
Notes	The full preceding word is <bezéichen-nísseda>. Also, what happens to the diphthong in */naud-/? It monophthongizes (if that is a word) into a long /o:/, because the morpheme ends in what type of obstruent? Also note [ú] from /u/ written as <í> in <nísseda>.	And here we have the opposite, a long /o:/ that diphthongizes (again, not sure that is a word).	A fronted vowel in the column to the left, but unfronted here and to the right. But is there any of that earlier raising (of /o/ to /u/), or did that only happen to short vowels?	Here your writer is assuming that <cnúegíu, knúog> are understood by Notker as single words, for spelling rules.

	<u>Word Initial, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Final</u>	<u>Word Final, Syl Final</u>
/Vk/ Morphemic	/gɪ/+/kuro:n+o:t+o:žɾ/	/brɪɛk+ɪn/	Not Found	/rokk/
Assign stress	[gɪ]+[kuró:n+o:t+o:žɾ]	[brɪɛk+ɪn]		[rókk]
Syllabification	[gɪ]+[kʊ.ró:.no:.to:žɾ]	[brɪɛ.kɪn]		
Raising				
Rounding				
Words assembled	[gɪ.kʊ.ró:.no:.to:žɾ]			
Fronting				
V-Reduction	[gɪ.kʊ.ró:.nʊ.to:žɾ]			
Fortition	[gɪ.kʊ.ró:.nʊ.to:št]	[prɪɛ.kɪn]		
Assimilation				
Epenthesis				
Lenition				
C-Reduction				[rók]
Elision				
Lowering				
Speech->Writing	<ge_corônotôst>	<prɪɛken>		<róg>
Variation				<rógh>
Miniscule	Mit kuóllichi unde mit êron gecorônost dû in . unde \ gesaxtost in uber diû uuerch dinero hando . Vber alliu diû \ in hîmele unde in érdo sint .	qui \ ora torquendo .i. prɪɛken machondo ridiculos motus \ i. sp̄ileliche_gebârda spectantibus præstant.		Est tunica alba .hęc non est afirmatio \ una . nec negatio una . Tanne neist \ nieht ein affirmatio . uuiz rógh ízzet . \ nóh ein lóugen .
Etymology	ELat <corona>	uncertain		VLat <roccus>
OHG lexeme	gikorōnōn	brieko		rok, 8
MHG lexeme	Not Found	brieke		roc
Latin gloss	'coronare'	'ōs torquere'		'tunica'
German gloss	'krönen'	'Fratze'		'Kutte'
English gloss	'crown'	'grimace'		'tunic'
Class	Verb wk (ō)	Noun wk (n)		Noun str (a)
Inflection	2nd sg past	masc acc pl		masc nom sg
Citattation	Np02602 : II, 21, 29	Nr07421 : I, 683, 5		Ni17203 : I, 523, 24
Notes	Latin generally stresses the penultimate (second to last) syllable. Given ELatin 'crown' in <coróna> (noun) and <coronāre> (verb), how can we tell that this came from the noun? Hint - by VLatin, vowel length became no longer separate from stress, as was in CLatin.	An unclear etymology here, and a good reminder that not all borrowed words came from Latin. And some may have just been made up by children, especailly maybe one for a silly facial expression.		A really interesting etymology here, about a word getting borrowed from Germanic into Romance, and then back into Germanic. To research, look up German <i>Rock</i> or even English <i>frock</i> . Notker even writes Latin <Rokkos>.

	<u>Word Initial, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Final</u>	<u>Word Final, Syl Final</u>
/Vh/ Morphemic	/tswɛj/+/hʉnt/	/tsi:h+ɛ+žɾ/	/gɪ+dru:h+t+o:n/	/dru:h/
Assign stress	[tswɛj]+[hʉnt]	[tsi:h+ɛ+žɾ]	[gɪ+drú:h+t+o:n]	[drú:h]
Syllabification	[tswɛj.hʉnt]	[tsi:.hɛžɾ]	[gɪ.drú:h.to:n]	
Raising	[tswǎj.hʉnt]			
Rounding				
Words assembled				
Fronting				
V-Reduction		[tsi:.hɛžɾ]		
Fortition				
Assimilation	[tswǎj.hʉnt]			
Epenthesis				
Lenition				
C-Reduction				
Elision	<zuéi hʉnt>			
Lowering		[tsiɛ.hɛšt]	[gɪ.drúɛh.to:n]	[drúɛh]
Speech->Writing		<zihɛst>	<gedrúohtôn>	<drúoh>
Variation			<gedrúhoton>	<druôh>
Miniscule	die ín zuéin folgeton . ducentos (zuei hʉnt) quinquaginta (funfzich) .	Á\de úbe dú dína chlága geskéinen máht réhta uué\sen . sô tóoug . táz tu sia fure zihɛst .	Intret in conspectu tuo gemitus compedito\rum . Fúre dih chóme der súftód dero gedrúhoton .	Sélbui diú corruptibilitas corporis \ ist suáre druôh . in déro álle guôte súftont . Den súftod pechéne dú .
Etymology	Gmc */twa-/, */hunda-/	Gmc */teiha-/	Gmc */prüh-/	Gmc */prüh-/
OHG lexeme	zweihunt	zīhan	druoh	druoh
MHG lexeme	zwei, hunt	zīhen	drû	drû
Latin gloss	'ducenti'	'criminari'	'compedire'	'compes'
German gloss	'zweihundert'	'zeihen'	'fesseln'	'Fessel'
English gloss	'two hundred'	'accuse'	'fetter'	'fetter'
Class	Number Cardinal	Verb str (1)	Verb wk (ō), past part	Noun str (i)
Inflection	uninflected	2nd sg pres	masc gen pl wk	fem nom sg
Citation	Np39721 : II, 453, 26	Nb12345 : I, 354, 24	Np29001 : II, 327, 14	Np29003 : II, 327, 16

Notes

The word for *two* has multiple forms, seen in English *two*, *twilight*, *twin*, and *twain*. How about *twist* or *twine*?

Note that your writer sees a lowering of /ij/ to [iɛ] here, where most scholars would see a shortening of /ij/ to [i].

This column, and the one to the right, show lowering of long, high vowels before a laryngeal (here one that is word internal).

Note that a spelling rule has both [h] and [x] marked as <h> word finally. Your writer argues this in SPN03, but not all scholars would agree.

	<u>Word Initial, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Final</u>	<u>Word Final, Syl Final</u>
/Vx/ Morphemic	/platun+its+i:/+/xɑ:d+e+n/	/gɪ+rɔx+n/	/un+gɪ+rɔx+n+iʒ/	/ɪr+rɪx/
Assign stress	[plàtun+íts+i:]+[xá:d+e+n]	[gɪ+róx+n]	[ún+gɪ+ròx+n+iž]	/ɪr+ríx/
Syllabification	[plà.tu.ní.tsi:.xá:.den]	[gɪ.ró.xən]	[ún.gɪ.ròx.niž]	[ɪr.ríx]
Raising				
Rounding				
Words assembled	[plà.tu.ní.tsi:.xá:den]			
Fronting				
V-Reduction	[plà.tu.ní.tsi:.xá:.dən]		[ún.gɪ.ròx.nəʒ]	[əɾ.ríx]
Fortition				
Assimilation			[ún.gɪ.ròx.nəʒ]	
Epenthesis				
Lenition				
C-Reduction				
Elision				
Lowering				
Speech->Writing	<platonici chāden>	<ge rōchen>	<ún ge rōchenes>	<er ríh>
Variation			<ungerōchenes>	<Irríh>
Miniscule	Uuánda ér íst in_ sínero ábsida ófto \ óberôro dero súnnun . ófto níderôro . sô platonici chāden .	Vuâr uerdent sie áber stum . âne in_hello . dar ir \ unreht allez kestillet uuirt . unde gerōchen?	DEVS VLTIONVM DOMINVS . DEVS VLTIONVM \ er niêht ungerōchenes ne-lāzzet . Got des keriches \ tēta baldo .	idest \ esau in die ierusalem . Irbúge Got in iudicio des áhtāris chin\do . \ Irríh dih an diên in die iudiciū . die christianis fiemt sint .
Etymology	Gmc */kweþan/	Gmc */wrekan/	Gmc */wrekan/	Gmc */wrekan/
OHG lexeme	kwedan, 3266	rehhan, 37	rehhan, 37	rehhan, 37
MHG lexeme	quēden	rēchen	rēchen	rēchen
Latin gloss	'dicere'	'vindicare'	'vindicare'	'vindicare'
German gloss	'sagen'	'rāchen'	'rāchen'	'rāchen'
English gloss	'say'	'avenge'	'avenge'	'avenge'
Class	Verb str (5)	Verb str (4), past part	Verb str (4), pres part	Verb str (4)
Inflection	3rd pl past	uninflected	neut gen sg	2nd sg imper
Citation	Nc11803 : I, 799, 21	Np09423 : II, 101, 6	Np34709 : II, 393, 22	Np50715 : II, 573, 22
Notes	Note that your writer has the Latin word stressed on the penultimate syllable, but otherwise following the sound rules of an Old Alemannic word.	Note how Syllabification introduces an epenthetic schwa here. Could your writer also have just made the nasal syllabic? Is there much of a difference?	Here the Carolingian miniscule has the Latin written in all capitals. Another Notker manuscript, a Bavarian copy of his Psalms in Vienna, has the Latin words all in red ink.	Again note the capital <I> in <Irríh>. Many reforms are introduced with Carolingian miniscule, like capitalization and spaces between words. This makes their manuscripts quite readable to us.

	<u>Word Initial, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Final</u>	<u>Word Final, Syl Final</u>
/V kx / Morphemic	Not Found	/gɪ+žm <u>akx</u> +id+e/	/gɪ+žm <u>akx</u> +m+ɪn/	/gɪ+žm <u>akx</u> /
Assign stress		[gɪ+žm <u>á</u> kx+id+e]	[gɪ+žm <u>á</u> kx+m+ɪn]	[gɪ+žm <u>á</u> kx]
Syllabification		[gɪ.žm <u>á</u> k.xɪ.de]	[gɪ.žm <u>á</u> kx.mɪn]	[gɪ.žm <u>á</u> kx]
Raising		[gɪ.žm <u>ä</u> k.xɪ.de]		
Rounding				
Words assembled				
Fronting				
V-Reduction		[gɪ.žm <u>ä</u> k.xɪ̃.de]	[gɪ.žm <u>á</u> kx.mən]	
Fortition		[kɪ.žm <u>ä</u> k.xɪ̃.de]		
Assimilation				
Epenthesis				
Lenition				
C-Reduction			[kɪ.žm <u>ak</u> .mən]	[gɪ.žm <u>ák</u>]
Elision				
Lowering				
Speech->Writing		<ke sm <u>é</u> cc <u>h</u> eda>	<ke sm <u>á</u> gmen>	<ge sm <u>á</u> g>
Variation				
Miniscule		also er oûh sîn sapientia (kesm <u>é</u> cheda) ist . uuanda er ín sie ge\tuỗt sapere (sm <u>é</u> chen) .	áfter íro \ íogelichero náhi . únde hártu geuu <u>é</u> hselotiu fone íro miske\lungo . hábeta sí lúzzel éigenes kesm <u>á</u> gmen .	Nu uuerde ín zúo-sehentem íro tísg in_stríg . \ Vbelen gesm <u>á</u> g práhton siê in mînen tísg . íro tísg sí íro stríg .
Etymology		*/smakkja-/	*/smakka-/	*/smakka-/
OHG lexeme		gismekkida, 1	gismakmo, 2	gismack, 4
MHG lexeme		gesmecken (verb)	gesmach	gesmach
Latin gloss		'sapientia'	'sapor'	'sapor'
German gloss		'Wahrnehmung'	'Geschmack'	'Geschmack'
English gloss		'perception'	'taste'	'taste'
Class		Noun str (ō)	Noun wk (n)	Noun str (a)
Inflection		fem nom sg	masc gen sg	masc acc sg
Citation		Np15310 : II, 167, 16	Nc02419 : I, 708, 24	Np24007 : II, 270, 10
Notes		A raised /a/ to [ä] here, followed by two forms to the right without raising. Also, the <k> is fortis, as this is a gloss, actually written above <sapientia>, and pronounced in isolation, not after <sîn>.	The [m] suffix is interesting, your writer is not sure if there are other examples.	An example of the spelling rule, where both [k] and [g] are marked <g> word finally. Most scholars have long accepted this one.

	<u>Word Initial, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Final</u>	<u>Word Final, Syl Final</u>
/lg/ Morphemic	/žede <u>l</u> /+/gáŋg+e+NŦ+iw/	/ɪr+bó <u>l</u> g+n+e:n/	/ba <u>l</u> g+/+t+o:n/	/ba <u>l</u> g/
Assign stress	[žéde <u>l</u>][+gáŋg+e+NŦ+iw]	[ɪr+bó <u>l</u> g+n+e:n]	[bá <u>l</u> g][+t+o:n]	[bá <u>l</u> g]
Syllabification	[žé.de <u>l</u>][+gáŋ.gəN.Ŧiw]	[ɪr.bó <u>l</u> .gne:n]	[bá <u>l</u> g][+to:n]	
Raising				
Rounding	[žé.de <u>l</u>][+gáŋ.gəN.Ŧü:]			
Words assembled	[žé.de <u>l</u> .gáŋ.gəN.Ŧü:]		[bá <u>l</u> g.to:n]	
Fronting				
V-Reduction	[žé.də <u>l</u> .gáŋ.gəN.Ŧü:]	[əɾ.bó <u>l</u> .gne:n]		
Fortition				[pá <u>l</u> g]
Assimilation	[žé.də <u>l</u> .gáŋ.gəN.Ŧü:]			
Epenthesis				
Lenition	[žé.də <u>l</u> .gáŋ.gəN.dü:]			
C-Reduction				
Elision	[žé.də <u>l</u> .gá:n.dü:]			
Lowering				
Speech->Writing	<séde <u>l</u> gândiu>	<erbó <u>l</u> genêŋ>	<bá <u>l</u> gtôn>	<pá <u>l</u> g>
Variation		<irbolgenen>	<bá <u>l</u> gton>	
Miniscule	Álde uuío uuéstert in séde <u>l</u> gândiu zéichen . áber chómên \ ad ortum . Tér hímel án dêmo siu stânt . tér trîbet siu úmbe .	Liberator meus de inimicis meis iracun\dis . Mîn irlósare fône irbolgenen fienden . scrîenten .	An fremeden Goten bá <u>l</u> gton siê ín . unde in leidsaminon gram\don sie ín .	Das sah Got . des palg er sih . uuan\da ín die balgton diê er ze sunen unde ze tohteron iruué\leta .
Etymology	Gmc */sepla/, */ganga-/	Gmc */belga-/	Gmc */balgja-/	Gmc */belga-/
OHG lexeme	gangan, 339	belgan, 40	belgen, 2	belgan, 40
MHG lexeme	gân	bêlgen	belgen	bêlgen
Latin gloss	'ire'	'irasci'	'ad iram provocare'	'irasci'
German gloss	'gehen'	'erzürnen'	'zum Zorn reizen'	'erzürnen'
English gloss	'go'	'get angry'	'provoke to anger'	'get angry'
Class	Verb anom, pres part	Verb str (3), past part	Verb wk (ja)	Verb str (3)
Inflection	neut nom pl	masc dat pl	3rd pl past	3rd sg past
Citation	Nb12011 : I, 14, 31	Np05523 : II, 56, 14	Np55815 : II, 627, 19	Np55824 : II, 627, 31
Notes	Compare <séde <u>l</u> > with English <i>sit</i> . Maybe this should be two morphemes /žed+al/, although likely not understood as such in Notker's time. What change in spelling might point to an underlying /žed+al/?	To understand this root more fully, think of English <i>bellows</i> , and how that tool inflates or swells up. Do people similarly breathe in and swell up when they get angry?	Think of the animals that people may have observed one or two thousand years ago. Do they make themselves larger when angry - cats puff up their fur and birds spread their feathers.	We had the German word <i>Zorn</i> earlier (and also to the left), and here you see a gloss <i>erzürnen</i> . Can you draw out the two changes needed to generate the /ü/ in the second from the /o/ in the first?

	<u>Word Initial, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Final</u>	<u>Word Final, Syl Final</u>
/lk/ Morphemic	Not Found	Not Found	Not Found	Not Found
Assign stress				
Syllabification				
Raising				
Rounding				
Words assembled				
Fronting				
V-Reduction				
Fortition				
Assimilation				
Epenthesis				
Lenition				
C-Reduction				
Elision				
Lowering				
Speech->Writing				
Variation				
Miniscule				
Etymology				
OHG lexeme				
MHG lexeme				
Latin gloss				
German gloss				
English gloss				
Class				
Inflection				
Cititation				
Notes		The borrowing from Greek <i>auricha</i> <u>lc</u> <i>um</i> would be a good candidate, but it comes across with the <lc> mapping to maybe [lx] in <orchol <u>ch</u> ine>.		

	<u>Word Initial, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Final</u>	<u>Word Final, Syl Final</u>
/lh/ Morphemic	/wider <u>h</u> o:r+i:g/	/bɪ+ve <u>l</u> h+e+NT+U/		/bɪ+va <u>l</u> h/
Assign stress	[wider <u>h</u> ò:r+i:g]	[bɪ+vél <u>h</u> +e+NT+U]		
Syllabification	[wí.dər <u>h</u> ò:.rí:g]	[bɪ.vél <u>h</u> ɛN.TU]		[bɪ.vá <u>l</u> h]
Raising				
Rounding				
Words assembled				
Fronting	[wí.dər <u>h</u> õ:.rí:g]			
V-Reduction	[wí.dər <u>h</u> õ:.rí:g]	[bɪ.vél <u>h</u> ɛN.TU]		
Fortition				[pɪ.vá <u>l</u> x]
Assimilation		[bɪ.vél <u>h</u> ɛN.TU]		
Epenthesis				
Lenition		[bɪ.vél <u>h</u> ɛN.du]		
C-Reduction				
Elision				
Lowering				
Speech->Writing	<uuider <u>h</u> ôrîg>	<beuél <u>h</u> endo>		<peuá <u>l</u> h>
Variation				
Miniscule	Diê legi (dero êo) uuider <u>h</u> ôrig uuâren . prophetas (uuîs-sâgen) \ sluôgen . unde nu christum slâhen uuêllen .	Τὰξ úr\lub káb ímo zeno . sîn lánt . iôh sîne líute . ze_sînen tríuuôn beuél <u>h</u> endo . Sô dioterih mít témo uuórte ze_italia chám .		Ταξ rûmiska \ hêrote uuólta síh chlâgon . mít príeuen ze_démo chéisere . dér dioteri\che ze_sînen tríuuôn daz lánt peuá <u>l</u> h .
Etymology	Gmc */wipra/, */hauz-/	Gmc */bifelha-/		Gmc */bifelha-/
OHG lexeme	widarhōrīg, 4	bifelahan, 122		bifelahan, 122
MHG lexeme	widerhærec	bevêlhen		bevêlhen
Latin gloss	'repugnans'	'committere'		'committere'
German gloss	'widersprüchlich'	'anvertrauen'		'anvertrauen'
English gloss	'contradictory'	'entrust'		'entrust'
Class	Adj	Verb str (3), pres part		Verb str (3)
Inflection	uninflected	neut gen pl (adv)		3rd sg past
Citation	Np12345 : II, 350, 14	Nb00625 : I, 6, 4		Nb02411 : I, 29, 22
Notes	Why did Notker not mark the long /õ:/ in /hõ:.rí:g/ as fronted, as is done in the MHG form <hærec>? Why not just write *<hêrîg> or *<hóirîg> instead of <hôrîg>? Why does he stick so closely to vowel graph patterns found in Latin?	Here again we see an epenthetic <e>, which your writer sees as a spelling rule, but others would understand as phonological.		Your writer has [h] moving to [x] when directly bordering a consonant (if no syllable boundary in between, unlike the earlier [bɪ.vél <u>h</u> ɛN.du]). But the change is more than fortition. How else do /h/ and /x/ differ? What about lenis and fortis /ž/ and /s/?

	<u>Word Initial, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Final</u>	<u>Word Final, Syl Final</u>
/lx/ Morphemic	/xnuTT+i <u>l</u> /+/ <u>x</u> anf+j+i <u>n</u> /	/we <u>l</u> x+i <u>ž</u> T+e/	/g <u>I</u> +wi <u>l</u> x+t+i <u>n</u> /	/we <u>l</u> x/
Assign stress	[xnuTT+i <u>l</u>]+[<u>x</u> anf+j+i <u>n</u>]	[we <u>l</u> x+i <u>ž</u> T+e]	[g <u>I</u> +wi <u>l</u> x+t+i <u>n</u>]	[we <u>l</u> x]
Syllabification	[xnuT.t <u>il</u>]+[<u>x</u> an.fj <u>in</u>]	[we <u>l</u> .x <u>i</u> .žte]	[g <u>I</u> .wi <u>l</u> x.t <u>in</u>]	
Raising	[xnuT.t <u>il</u>]+[<u>x</u> än.fj <u>in</u>]			
Rounding				
Words assembled	[xnuT.t <u>il</u> .x <u>än</u> .fj <u>in</u>]			
Fronting	[xnuT.t <u>il</u> .x <u>än</u> .fj <u>in</u>]			
V-Reduction	[xnuT.t <u>il</u> .x <u>än</u> .fən]	[we <u>l</u> .x <u>ĩ</u> .žte]	[g <u>I</u> .wi <u>l</u> x.tən]	
Fortition	[xnuT.t <u>il</u> .x <u>än</u> .fən]	[we <u>l</u> .x <u>ĩ</u> .šte]		
Assimilation	[xnuT.t <u>il</u> .x <u>äm</u> .fən]			
Epenthesis	[xnuT.t <u>il</u> .x <u>äm</u> .pfən]			
Lenition				
C-Reduction				
Elision				
Lowering				
Speech->Writing	<chnüttel <u>ch</u> émfen>	<uu <u>él</u> chesta>	<geuu <u>il</u> hten>	<uu <u>él</u> h>
Variation			<geuu <u>il</u> chten>	
Miniscule	Ut pugillatores . uel cursores dicuntur . non quod sint \ dispositi . sed quod habeant potentiam hoc facile facien\di . Álsô die genémmet uuérdent chnüttel <u>ch</u> émfen .	Únde uuáz óuh tés . táx sie dax uu <u>él</u> chesta \ sô dax márg íst . ze_íinnerôst pérgent . mít tero úzerûn hólzes fësti .	únde den nioman ferbréchen \ ne-mág . áne geuu <u>il</u> chten ín demo búcc'hinen blúote .	Similiter autem \ his et molle et durum se habet . Tien íst kelih . uu <u>él</u> h . \ únde herte .
Etymology	Gmc */knup-/, CLat <campus>	Gmc */welka-/	Gmc */welkja-/	Gmc */welka-/
OHG lexeme	knuttilkempfo	welk	wilken	welk
MHG lexeme	knütel + kempfe	wëlc	wilken	wëlc
Latin gloss	'pugillator'	'mollis'	'emollire'	'mollis'
German gloss	'Faustkämpfer'	'weich'	'erweichen'	'weich'
English gloss	'boxer'	'soft'	'soften'	'soft'
Class	Noun wk (n)	Adj	Verb wk (ja), past part	Adj
Inflection	masc nom pl	neut acc sg superl wk	masc acc sg	uninflected
Citation	Nk09714 : I, 452, 18	Nb16713 : I, 202, 20	Nc06914 : I, 753, 28	Nk09724 : I, 452, 29
Notes	Your writer has [xäm.pfən] deriving from Latin <campus>. How is that partially incorrect? There are many derivations of <camp-> in Latin. What additional letter would a variation need, in order to generate the main vowel in <ch <u>é</u> mfen>?	We talked about an earlier raising, of /e/ to /i/ before /j,i/. So why is this word <uu <u>él</u> chesta> and not <uu <u>il</u> chesta>? See the column to the right to get even more confused.	Skip to the next page. Should not this past participle (if uninflected) have a /ja/ in the form, and so geminate /kk/ that became /kx/? But if so, your writer would expect <geuu <u>il</u> gten> here. Why?	Earlier we mentioned how [x] and [h] are written <h> word finally. But why pick <h> and not <ch>? To maybe answer, look for longer consonant clusters in Latin (or for that matter, in another Romance language that you may know, like Modern Spanish)?

	<u>Word Initial, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Final</u>	<u>Word Final, Syl Final</u>
/lkx/ Morphemic	Not Found	/wílkx+jɛ+t/	Not Found	Not Found
Assign stress		[wílkx+jɛ+t]		
Syllabification		[wílk.xjɛt]		
Raising				
Rounding				
Words assembled				
Fronting				
V-Reduction		[wílk.xət]		
Fortition				
Assimilation				
Epenthesis				
Lenition				
C-Reduction				
Elision				
Lowering				
Speech->Writing		<uuílchet>		
Variation				
Miniscule		Ér íst mulciens ferrum . dǫz chít \ er uuílchet taz ísen mít temo fiure .		
Etymology		Gmc */welkja-/		
OHG lexeme		wilken		
MHG lexeme		wilken		
Latin gloss		'emollire'		
German gloss		'erweichen'		
English gloss		'soften'		
Class		Verb wk (ja)		
Inflection		3rd sg pres		
Cititation		Nc02822 : I, 711, 28		
Notes		Earlier we wrote about gemination (a doubling) of obstruents before a /j/. That could explain why your writer posits /kx/ here. But why the <í> in <uuílchet>, given <é> above in <uuélh>?		

	<u>Word Initial, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Final</u>	<u>Word Final, Syl Final</u>
/rg/ Morphemic	/akxer+gang/	/marg+ɪ/	/ɪr+wurg+t+o:n/	/marg/
Assign stress	[ákxer+gàng]	[márg+ɪ]	/ɪr+wúrg+t+o:n/	[márg]
Syllabification	[ák.xer.gàng]	[már.gɪ]	[ɪr.wúrg.to:n]	
Raising				
Rounding				
Words assembled				
Fronting				
V-Reduction	[ák.xər.gàng]		[əɪr.wúrg.to:n]	
Fortition				
Assimilation	[ák.xər.gàng]			
Epenthesis				
Lenition				
C-Reduction				
Elision				
Lowering				
Speech->Writing	<áccher_gáng>	<máрге>	<er-uuúrgtôn>	<márg>
Variation	<ácher_gáng>		<ir-uuurgton>	
Miniscule	Ut si quis fodiens humum causa colendi agri . inueniat \ pondus defossi auri . Sô dax íst . úbe ioman dúrh ácher-gáng an dia ér\da bréchende . éin fúnt cóldes findet .	únde súgent taz sóu . mít tien uuúrzellôn . únde sie dännân sô úf\ íro stárchí áfter demo máрге .	adducet dominus cum operantibus iniustitiam . \ Diê sih an dia gelíchi chêrent déro iruuurgton . unde fone ube\len úbel lírnênt .	táz sie dax uuélchesta \ sô dax márg íst . ze_innerôst pérgent . mít tero úzerún bólzes fêsti . ún\de diu rínda ze*_úzerôst .
Etymology	Gmc */akra-/, */ganga-/	Gmc */mazga-/	Gmc */wurgja-/	Gmc */mazga-/
OHG lexeme	akkargang	marg	irwürgen	marg
MHG lexeme	ackerganc	marc	erwürgen	marc
Latin gloss	'cultus agri'	'medulla'	'strangulare'	'medulla'
German gloss	'Ackerbau'	'Knochenmark'	'erwürgen'	'Knochenmark'
English gloss	'agriculture'	'marrow'	'strangle'	'marrow'
Class	Noun str (a)	Noun str (a)	Verb wk (ja), past part	Noun str (a)
Inflection	masc acc sg	neut dat sg	masc gen pl wk	neut nom sg
Citattation	Nb23509 : I, 308, 5	Nb16710 : I, 202, 14	Np49103 : II, 555, 15	Nb16714 : I, 202, 20
Notes	Continuing on with Latin spelling patterns, Notker writes <cch> for [kx] word internally, to distinguish that from [x], which is written <ch>. But often [kx] is written <ch> too, as here. Why would he lean towards shorter consonant clusters?	You can see how consonants seem to soften in English, and harden in German. Like the words <i>Sorge</i> and <i>sorrow</i> , here <i>Mark</i> and <i>marrow</i> , and even <i>durch</i> and <i>through</i> .	Given that softening, how could English <i>worry</i> relate to German <i>erwürgen</i> ? And why a different ending in <i>worry</i> than in <i>sorrow</i> and <i>marrow</i> ?	In Germanic, the /ž/, which is confusingly spelled in Notker as <s>, often alternates with /r/. You see this in some obvious English pairs, like <i>was</i> and <i>were</i> , but also in some less obvious ones, like <i>lose</i> and <i>forlorn</i> .

	<u>Word Initial, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Final</u>	<u>Word Final, Syl Final</u>
/rk/ Morphemic	Not Found	/ja:r+mèr <u>k</u> et+i/	Not Found	Not Found
Assign stress		[já:r+mèr <u>k</u> et+i]		
Syllabification		[já:r.mèr <u>k</u> e.ti]		
Raising				
Rounding				
Words assembled				
Fronting				
V-Reduction				
Fortition				
Assimilation				
Epenthesis				
Lenition				
C-Reduction				
Elision				
Lowering				
Speech->Writing		<iâr mé <u>r</u> kate>		
Variation		<iâr mé <u>r</u> cate>		
		also chóuflute strîtent . / táz tér chóuf súle uuésen stâte . dér ze _iâr-mé <u>r</u> cate / getân uuirdet . er sí réht . álde únreh̄t .		
Miniscule				
Etymology		ELat <mercatus>		
OHG lexeme		jārmarkāt, 7		
MHG lexeme		jārmarket		
Latin gloss		'mercationes annuae'		
German gloss		'Jahrmarkt'		
English gloss		'annual fair'		
Class		Noun: masc str (a)		
Inflection		dat sg		
Citation		Nb05816 : I, 69, 7		
Notes		The word for 'trident' is also often cited here - <fúrkûn>, from Latin <i>furca</i> . There Notker wrote the [k] from <i>furca</i> as <k>, but here he picked <c>, following the Latin in <mer <u>c</u> atus>.	Do you see a reason for the choice of <k> versus <c>, or is it just variation?	CLatin <i>merc<u>a</u>tus</i> had a long /a/, but the distinction in length disappeared in VLatin. Does this unmarked <a> in <iâr mé <u>r</u> cate> reflect VLatin /a/, or an Old Alemannic reduction to [e], or is it really [a:] and Notker just forgot to put a diacritic on <â>?

	<u>Word Initial, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Final</u>	<u>Word Final, Syl Final</u>
/rh/ Morphemic	/un+gɪ+war+hɛjt/	/vurh+i/	/naht+/vorht+o:n/	Not Found
Assign stress	[ún+gɪ+wàr+hɛjt]	[vúr+hǐ]	[náht]+[vórht+o:n]	
Syllabification	[ún.gɪ.wár.hɛjt]	[vúr.hǐ]	[náht]+[vórh.to:n]	
Raising	[ún.gɪ.wár.hǎjt]			
Rounding				
Words assembled			[náht.vòrh.to:n]	
Fronting		[vúr.hǐ]		
V-Reduction		[vúr.hɪ]		
Fortition			[náxt.fòrx.to:n]	
Assimilation	[ún.gɪ.wár.hǎjt]			
Epenthesis				
Lenition				
C-Reduction				
Elision				
Lowering				
Speech->Writing	<ún ge uuáre héit>	<uúrehe>	<náht fórhôn>	
Variation		<fúrehe>		
Miniscule	Temeritas \ íst úmbe-déncheda . únde úngeuuáreheit . únde gâscrécchi . únde únórden\hafri . fráuali . únúnderskéit . únrihti .	fōne ánaǵénne únz in úz . tíu héizet series á serendo . nâh tes áchermánnes \ sáhenne . dér hína áfter déro léngi dero fúrehe sáhet . únz er dúrhkât .	Non timebis á timore nocturno . °a sagitta uo\lante per diem . Fōne diú ne-furhtest dú fore náht-forhton . dax siNT \ úngeuuízzene sunða .	
Etymology	Gmc */warō/, */haidu-/	Gmc */furh-/	Gmc */naht/, */furhtō-/	
OHG lexeme	ungiwaraheit	furh	nahtforhta	
MHG lexeme	ungewarheit	vurch	nahtvorhte	
Latin gloss	'incuria'	'sulcus'	'timor nocturnus'	
German gloss	'Nachlässigkeit'	'Furche'	'Angst vor der Nacht'	
English gloss	'carelessness'	'furrow'	'fear of the night'	
Class	Noun str (i)	Noun str (i)	Noun wk (n)	
Inflection	fem nom sg	fem gen sg	fem dat pl	
Citation	Nb23327 : I, 306, 4	Nb21630 : I, 280, 22	Np33907 : II, 384, 16	
Notes	You are familiar with German <i>wahr</i> as 'true', but there is also the verb <i>wahrnehmen</i> , to 'take in the truth' or 'perceive'. English <i>perceive</i> has Latin 'take' in it, <i>per + capere</i> . Are they linked, perhaps one a translation of the other? Or maybe not.	With /lh/ we had a similar spelling pattern.	Your writer takes a very conservative view here, with [x] not from /x/ but from /h/ via fortition. The diphthong in <liēhti> 'light' is why. How would <h> in <náhtes> be pronounced, per his analysis?	The nom sg of 'furrow' would be /vurh/, written <uúrh>. Given the pattern after /rh/, what do you think the <h> here would reflect, an [h] in [vúrh] an [x] in [vúrx]? Or maybe something else, like [vúrah]?

	<u>Word Initial, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Final</u>	<u>Word Final, Syl Final</u>
/rx/ Morphemic	/hɪntɛr/+/xɔ:ž+o:+nɪtɪ+ɪn/	/žtarx+ir+o:n/	/žtarx/+/t+e/	/žtarx/
Assign stress	[hɪntɛr]+[xɔ:ž+o:+nɪtɪ+ɪn]	[žtárx+ir+o:n]	[žtárx]+[t+e]	[žtárx]
Syllabification	[hɪn.tɛr]+[xɔ:.žo:nɪ.tɪn]	[žtár.xɪ.ro:n]		
Raising				
Rounding				
Words assembled	[hɪn.tɛr.xɔ:.žo:nɪ.tɪn]		[žtárx.te]	
Fronting		[žtár.xɪ.ro:n]		
V-Reduction	[hɪn.tɛr.xɔ:.žənt.tən]			
Fortition	[hɪn.tɛr.xɔ:.žənt.tən]	[štár.xɪ.ro:n]	[štárx.te]	[štárx]
Assimilation	[hɪn.tɛr.xɔ:.žənt.tən]			
Epenthesis				
Lenition	[hɪn.dɛr.xɔ:.žənt.tən]			
C-Reduction				
Elision				
Lowering				
Speech->Writing	<hinder-chôsonten>	<stárcherôn>	<stárhta>	<stárh>
Variation		<stárcheron>		
Miniscule	Detrahentem secreto proximo suo . hunc persequer . Hín\derchôsonten man ándermo iágeta ih . unde áhta sîn . uuanda \ diu persecutio (áhtunga) guôt ist .	Eripiens in\opem de manu fortiorum eius . Den hábelôsen erzúcchendo û\zer sînero stárcheron hánden .	gót únde gûot . sâligheit ún\de ein . déro sînt fieriu . déro iogelich stárhta dâz ánder .	únde slíhtî . únde héui . \ Únde uerním óuh nóh mēr . Úbe díu corpo\ra sô stárh sînt . táz síu uuíchen nemúgen .
Etymology	Gmc */hindar/, CLat <causāri>	Gmc */starka-/	Gmc */starkja-/	Gmc */starka-/
OHG lexeme	hintarkōsōn, 1	stark, 90	sterken, 46	stark, 90
MHG lexeme	hinderkosen	starc	sterken	starc
Latin gloss	'detrahere'	'fortis'	'roborare'	'fortis'
German gloss	'verleumden'	'stark'	'stärken'	'stark'
English gloss	'slander'	'strong'	'strengthen'	'strong'
Class	Verb wk (ō), pres part	Adj	Verb wk (ja)	Adj
Inflection	acc sg masc	gen pl comp wk	3rd sg past	uninflected
Citation	Np36701 : II, 417, 26	Np11013 : II, 118, 13	Nb17717 : I, 219, 17	Nk04608 : I, 404, 7
Notes	In English we have the phrase <i>talk behind someone's back</i> , which means the same as the glosses here. This is a word created by Notker, as it only occurs once in OHG. And he invented almost the same phrase as we have today.	Note raising in the comparative in modern German, <i>stark</i> , <i>stärker</i> , but not here. Note raising in modern German <i>verstärken</i> and also on the next page.	Again, raising (called a-umlaut, or primary umlaut) is heavily covered in the history of German, and the disputes often center around words like these.	Note the spelling patterns for [rx] in these last three columns - <rch> in the middle of a word, <rh> before a third consonant, and <rh> word finally. Does Notker have some rule where he only writes three consonants word internally, and two word finally?

	<u>Word Initial, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Final</u>	<u>Word Final, Syl Final</u>
/r k / Morphemic	Not Found	/žtar <u>k</u> x+jē+NTT+IN/	Not Found	Not Found
Assign stress		[žtár <u>k</u> x+jē+NTT+IN]		
Syllabification		[žtár <u>k</u> .xjēNT.TIN]		
Raising		[žtär <u>k</u> .xjēNT.TIN]		
Rounding				
Words assembled				
Fronting				
V-Reduction		[žtär <u>k</u> .xəNT.tən]		
Fortition		[štär <u>k</u> .xəNT.tən]		
Assimilation		[štär <u>k</u> .xəNT.tən]		
Epenthesis				
Lenition				
C-Reduction				
Elision				
Lowering				
Speech->Writing		<stér <u>ch</u> enten>		
Variation				
Miniscule		Tû neuíndest áber nehéinen . \ díu zuéi skídōnten . únde daz éina stér <u>ch</u> en\ten .		
Etymology		Gmc */starkja-/		
OHG lexeme		sterken, 46		
MHG lexeme		sterken		
Latin gloss		'roborare'		
German gloss		'stärken'		
English gloss		'strengthen'		
Class		Verb wk (ja), pres part		
Inflection		acc sg masc		
Citation		Ni18407 : I, 525, 25		
Notes	Following up with the last page, why not <rcch> here, if really reflecting [r k]? To answer, maybe reflect that God's words have been transmitted to Notker via Latin texts. As he reads these words, he takes in their spelling patterns.	And if Notker's readers are all Old Alemannic native speakers anyway, would they need an exact phonetic spelling to pronounce a word?	If not, when spelling his own Old Alemannic, how can Notker make those words draw nearer to the divine?	Your writer believes that Notker does this by making Old Alemannic words look more Latin - by simplifying the consonant clusters, especially at the borders of words, where those clusters are most noticeable.

	<u>Word Initial, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Final</u>	<u>Word Final, Syl Final</u>
/ng/ Morphemic	/i <u>n</u> +g <u>I</u> +žläh+e+n <u>T</u> /	/l <u>an</u> g+j <u>e</u> +t/	/hine+l <u>an</u> g/+/t+e/	/j <u>un</u> g+il+i <u>ng</u> /
Assign stress	[i <u>n</u> +g <u>I</u> +žläh+e+n <u>T</u>]	[l <u>an</u> g+j <u>e</u> +t]	[híne+l <u>an</u> g]+[t+e]	[júng+il+l <u>ing</u>]
Syllabification	[i <u>n</u> .g <u>I</u> .žläh.n <u>h</u> en <u>T</u>]	[l <u>an</u> .g <u>j</u> et]	[hí.ne.l <u>an</u> g].[te]	[jún.gi.l <u>ing</u>]
Raising		[l <u>ä</u> n.g <u>j</u> et]		
Rounding				
Words assembled			[hí.ne.l <u>an</u> g.te]	
Fronting				[jún.gi.l <u>ing</u>]
V-Reduction	[i <u>n</u> .g <u>I</u> .žläh.n <u>h</u> en <u>T</u>]	[l <u>ä</u> n.g <u>ə</u> t]		[jún.gi.l <u>ing</u>]
Fortition				
Assimilation	[i <u>n</u> .g <u>I</u> .žläh.n <u>h</u> en <u>T</u>]	[l <u>ä</u> ŋ.g <u>ə</u> t]	[hí.ne.l <u>an</u> g.te]	[júŋ.gi.l <u>ing</u>]
Epenthesis				
Lenition				
C-Reduction				
Elision	[i <u>n</u> .g <u>I</u> .žläh:n <u>T</u>]			
Lowering				
Speech->Writing	<i <u>n</u> _ge slähent>	<l <u>en</u> get>	<hína l <u>an</u> gta>	<iúngeling>
Variation	<i <u>n</u> _ge slähent>			
Miniscule	Quę dira penitus meant . nec nocentia corpori . mentis uulnere seuiunt . Tīe tīefōr \ i <u>ng</u> eslähent . nōh liden netārōnt . nūbe des sīnnes ähtent .	Uuānda si mīr āber nū gesuichen hābet . \ nū l <u>en</u> get mīna urīst . mīn ārbēit-sāmo līb . Quid totiens \ iactastis me felicem amici?	Áber \ des uuúnderōta síh tíu mánigi . díu síh fōre mícheli hína\l <u>an</u> gta zuō mīlá . sō syrus chād . táz sí geslāpfa uuórtel <u>ni</u> cyllenii .	Téro zuéio uuás ter fōrderoro éin \ rōt iúngeling . uuānda sīn stérno rōt íst . únde slíndāre \ íoh túrstesare des plúotes .
Etymology	Gmc */slaha-/	Gmc */langja-/	Gmc */langja-/	Gmc */jungilinga-/
OHG lexeme	ingislahan, 1	lengen, 24	hinalengen, 1	jungiling, 8
MHG lexeme	slahen	lengen	lengen	jüngelinc
Latin gloss	'inferare'	'prolongare'	'extendere'	'adulescens'
German gloss	'eindringen'	'verlängern'	'sich hinziehen'	'Jüngling'
English gloss	'intrude'	'lengthen'	'drag on'	'adolescent'
Class	Verb str (6)	Verb wk (ja)	Verb wk (ja)	Noun str (a)
Inflection	3rd pl pres	3rd sg pres	3rd sg past	masc nom sg
Citation	Nb20014 : I, 253, 25	Nb00716 : I, 8, 20	Nc14806 : I, 828, 10	Nc07317 : I, 757, 27
Notes	Another monk, and writer in OHG, is named Otfrid. He also struggled with German consonants, and even describes that his <z> sounds like <i>stridor dentium</i> . That can translate as 'gnashing of teeth', which, plus wailing, are the noises of the damned.	Search for 'Otfrid's letter to Archbishop Liudbert'. Otfrid also struggles with how German words do not have the same gender as Latin ones.	Notker writes a similar letter, and also to an ecclesiastical elder, Bishp Hugo of Sitten. It is less colorful, but also addresses the same struggle.	Both letters are translated from Latin, and a lot of fun to read. When reading in translation, keep a copy of the original Latin nearby, to catch some of the more colorful phrases.

	<u>Word Initial, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Final</u>	<u>Word Final, Syl Final</u>
/nk/ Morphemic	/mann+ižk+ijn+e:n/+/korp̥ur+o:n/	/vier/+/tsiŋk+u:n/	/tiŋkt/+/u:n/	NF
Assign stress	[mán+ižk+ijn+e:n]+[kór̥p̥ur+o:n]	[víer̥]+[tsíŋk+u:n]	[tíŋkt̥]+[u:n]	
Syllabification	[mán.nĩ.žki.j.ne:n]+[kór̥.p̥u.ro:n]	[víer̥]+[tsíŋ.ku:n]		
Raising	[mǎn.nĩ.žki.j.ne:n]+[kór̥.p̥u.ro:n]			
Rounding				
Words assembled	[mǎn.nĩ.žki.j.ne:n.kór̥.p̥u.ro:n]	[víer̥.tsíŋ.ku:n]	[tíŋk.tu:n]	
Fronting				
V-Reduction	[mǎn.nĩ.žki.j.ne:n.kór̥.p̥u.ro:n]			
Fortition	[mǎn.nĩ.ški.j.ne:n.kór̥.p̥u.ro:n]	[víer̥.tsíŋ.ku:n]		
Assimilation	[mǎn.nĩ.ški.j.ne:n.kór̥.p̥u.ro:n]	[víer̥.tsíŋ̩.ku:n]	[tíŋk̩.tu:n]	
Epenthesis				
Lenition				
C-Reduction				
Elision				
Lowering				
Speech->Writing	<méniskinên górp̥orôn>	<uier zínkûn>	<tínctûn>	
Variation	<méniskinên górp̥otôn>	<fier zínkun>	<tínctun>	
Miniscule	Târ sizzent in_íro mén\iskinên górp̥otôn . die manes héizent a manando . daz chît rúnsige . uuánda sie rúnnen fône íro fôrderôn sâmen .	Uuáz uuíle ánderes tíu fêstenunga phitagore . dér día fier\zínkun méisterscáft lêrta .	Erantque quidam \ sacra nigredine colorati . Uuâren súmelichiu mít tínctun gescri\beniu .	
Etymology	ELat <corpus, corpora>	Gmc */fedwōr/, unknown	ELat <tinctus>	
OHG lexeme	gorpoto, gorporo, 1	fiorzinki, 1	tinkta, 22	
MHG lexeme	Not found	vier, zinke	tincte	
Latin gloss	'corpus'	'quaternarius'	'atramentum'	
German gloss	'Körper'	'vierteilig'	'Tinte'	
English gloss	'body'	'four part'	'ink'	
Class	Noun wk (n).	Adj (j).	Noun wk (n).	
Inflection	masc dat pl	fem acc sg wk	fem dat sg	
Citation	Nc14117 : I, 822, 15	Nc09507 : I, 778, 10	Nc12307 : I, 806, 15	
Notes	Well, now you know the relationship between German <i>Mann</i> and <i>Mensch</i> . In Yiddish, the latter word means 'a person of integrity', and has carried that meaning into American English. Also note [r] mis-transcribed as <r> in <górp̥otôn>.	Another difficult etymology with /tsiŋk+u:n/, especially since it looks so similar to 'cinco' in Spanish. But how could that make any sense? Also hard is <ístúncôt> 'stuff' I, 86, 10, but a <g> in MHG <i>stun̩gen</i> ?	The Latin <i>tinctus</i> is a past participle, from a Latin infinitive <i>tingere</i> . Think of English <i>tinge</i> . A /g/ becomes [k] in certain places in Notker. Did Latin once have a similar process?	We used to have <i>tinctus</i> in English too, as <i>tinct</i> . But now we say <i>tint</i> ? Maybe we just shortened it to make it easier to say, or maybe some other language did and we just borrowed their word. Word etymologies are not always an exact science.

	<u>Word Initial, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Final</u>	<u>Word Final, Syl Final</u>
/nh/ Morphemic	/li:xam+haf+t+i:g+e/	NF	NF	NF
Assign stress	[lí:xäm+hàf+t+i:g+e]			
Syllabification	[lí:.xäm.hàf.ti:.ge]			
Raising				
Rounding				
Words assembled				
Fronting				
V-Reduction	[lí:xěm.hàf.tr̥.ge]			
Fortition				
Assimilation				
Epenthesis				
Lenition				
C-Reduction				
Elision				
Lowering				
Speech->Writing	<lîcham_háftiga>			
Variation				
Miniscule	Quando (danne) corporale (diz lichamhaftiga) hoc induet (an sih légit) in-corruptionem (unlichamhafti) . et (unde) mortale (diz\ tôdigā) hoc in-mortalitatem (an sih légit úntôdigi) .			
Etymology	*/līkaham-/			
OHG lexeme	līhamhaftig, 4			
MHG lexeme	līcham haft			
Latin gloss	'corporeus'			
German gloss	'körperlich'			
English gloss	'corporeal'			
Class	Adj.			
Inflection	neut nom sg wk			
Citation	Np12345 : II, 352, 1			
Notes	Note that there is no nasal assimilation here before /h/, so no [ŋ] in [lí:xěm.hàf.tr̥.ge]. The /h/, although paired with /x/, is not actually a velar consonant corresponding to the velar /ŋ/. It is laryngeal, more breathy, not really pronounced in the mouth cavity.			

	<u>Word Initial, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Final</u>	<u>Word Final, Syl Final</u>
/NX/ Morphemic	/gagen+xe:r+t+e:n/	/triN(k)x+e+NTT+e:n/	/tran(k)x+/+t+o:žt/	/voll+e+tran(k)x/
Assign stress	[gágen+xè:r+t+e:n]	[triN(k)x+e+NTT+e:n]		[vóll+e+tràn(k)x]
Syllabification	[gá.gən.xè:r.te:n]	[triN(k).xəNT.te:n]	[trán(k)x].[to:žt]	[vól.le.tràn(k)x]
Raising				
Rounding				
Words assembled			[trán(k)x.to:žt]	
Fronting				
V-Reduction	[gá.gən.xè:r.te:n]	[triN(k).xəNT.te:n]		
Fortition		[triN(k).xəNT.te:n]	[trán(k)x.to:št]	
Assimilation	[gá.gəŋ.xè:r.te:n]	[triŋ(k).xəNT.te:n]	[trán(k)x.to:št]	[vól.le.trànŋ(k)x]
Epenthesis	[gá.gəŋk.xè:r.te:n]	[triŋ(k).xəNT.te:n]	[tránkx.to:št]	[vól.le.trànŋkx]
Lenition				
C-Reduction		[triŋk.xəNT.te:n]	[tránk.to:št]	[vól.le.trànŋk]
Elision				
Lowering				
Speech->Writing	<gágen chêrtên>	<trínchentên>	<trángtôst>	<fólle tráng>
Variation				
Miniscule	Álliu relatiua sínt tãnne gespróchen \ ze_íro gágen chêrtên . úbe siu réhto gespró\chen \ uuérdent .	álsó óuh tíu sélba ába túot tien sêlon post mortem dâr trínchentên .	Ροτα\sti nos uino conpunctionis . Trangtost unsih mit démo uuíne ge\stúngedo .	únde sí dúrstegiu fóne árbeiten . únde fóre ángisten . bráh únde \ chórota . únde sí nío sô gúotes ne-inbéiz . sô fólle- tráng sí iz .
Etymology	Gmc */karja-/	Gmc */drenka-/	Gmc */drankjan/	Gmc */fullō-/ , */drenka-/
OHG lexeme	gagankēren, 4	trinkan, 137	trenken, 21	follatrinkan, 1
MHG lexeme	kēren	trinken	trenken	volle, trinken
Latin gloss	'convertere'	'bibere'	'madefacere'	'exaurire'
German gloss	'entgegen kehren'	'trinken'	'tränken'	'austrinken'
English gloss	'turn towards'	'drink'	'drench'	'drink up'
Class	Verb wk (ja), past part.	Verb str (3), pres part.	Verb wk (ja).	Verb str (3).
Inflection	neut dat pl	fem dat pl	2nd sg past	3rd sg past
Citation	Nk07326 : I, 430, 16	Nc010518 : I, 788, 8	Np20410 : II, 227, 4	Nc12914 : I, 810, 18

Notes

We are nearing the end of our list, and this Germanic root */karja-/ looks like our first root, */gabarja-/. However the root vowels in Notker are different - <gágenchêrtên> versus <ke**â**rda>. Why? Maybe your writer just made a mistake.

On this and the next two, you see an optional (k) before the [x]. If you reconstruct with or without the [k], do you end up with a different form?

Your writer practices "posit the least possible", which is different from structural linguistics, which focuses on reconstructing the phonemes.

Your writer very much believes in the existence of phonemes, but prefers to posit either /kx/ or /x/ rather than pick one, if spelling patterns allow. This is, again, positing the least possible, from SPN01.

	<u>Word Initial, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Initial</u>	<u>Word Internal, Syl Final</u>	<u>Word Final, Syl Final</u>
/ŋkx/ Morphemic	Not found	Not found	Not found	Not found
Assign stress				
Syllabification				
Raising				
Rounding				
Words assembled				
Fronting				
V-Reduction				
Fortition				
Assimilation				
Epenthesis				
Lenition				
C-Reduction				
Elision				
Lowering				
Speech->Writing				
Variation				
Miniscule				
Etymology				
OHG lexeme				
MHG lexeme				
Latin gloss				
German gloss				
English gloss				
Class				
Inflection				
Cititation				
Notes				